

1 **Crystal and shape preferred orientation producing anisotropy in** 2 **Slates from Northern Spain**

3 H.-R. Wenk^{a*}, J. Huang^{a,b}, M. Devoe^a, J. Gomez-Barreiro^c, Y. Ren^{d,e}, S. Barrios-Sánchez^c, R.
4 Vasin^f

5

6 ^a Department of Earth and Planetary Science, University of California, Berkeley, California

7 ^b Department of Earth Science, Institute of Disaster Prevention, Yanjiao, Sanhe, Hebei Province,
8 P.R. China

9 ^c Dpto. de Geología, University of Salamanca, Salamanca, Spain

10 ^d Advanced Photon Source, Argonne National Laboratory, Lemont, Illinois;

11 ^e Department of Physics, City University of Hong Kong, Kowloon, Hong Kong

12 ^f Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Frank Laboratory of Neutron Physics, Dubna, Russia

13 *Corresponding author e-mail address wenk@berkeley.edu (H.-R. Wenk)

14

15 **ABSTRACT**

16 Slates are common metasedimentary rocks in the Iberian Peninsula, ranging in age from
17 Proterozoic to Ordovician. Spain is currently the primary producer of high-quality slate products.
18 The excellent cleavage is related to microstructures with very strong preferred orientation of
19 muscovite and chlorite. In this study we explore preferred orientation of eleven slates of different
20 composition and metamorphic grade from Northern Spain with high energy synchrotron X-ray
21 diffraction and study microstructures with scanning electron microscopy. While phyllosilicates
22 display high crystal and shape preferred orientation, quartz, with also highly flattened grains, has
23 in most samples a random crystal orientation. The microstructural and texture data are used to
24 model anisotropic seismic properties with a self-consistent method and explore the influence of
25 crystal shapes on elastic anisotropy. Anisotropy for these slates is very high, compared with
26 gneiss and shale, and due to its prevalence, slate anisotropy contributes significantly to seismic
27 anisotropy in the upper crust.

28 **Keywords:** Slate, Crystal and shape preferred orientation, Texture, Seismic anisotropy

29 **Introduction**

30 Slates are remarkable metamorphic rocks with an often-perfect planar cleavage that extends
31 over large distances and allows to prepare plates several millimeters in thickness that can be used
32 for roofs, floors and walls. We originally became fascinated with slates when we analyzed
33 preferred orientation of a slate from the Belgian Ardennes and documented a texture strength of
34 muscovite with a maximum of over 100 multiples of random distribution (Wenk et al., 2019).
35 This exceeds the textures of most materials, including rolled metal foils and recrystallized metals
36 (Hutchinson and Nes, 1992). It is even more remarkable since slates are fine-grained polyphase
37 materials, generally composed of muscovite, chlorite, quartz and accessories.

38 In a review we explored the history of slate crystallographic preferred orientation (CPO)
39 which was very popular in the 1970s (Wenk et al., 2020). The unique cleavage properties of slate
40 caught early the attention of geologists who investigated slates and slaty cleavage first with
41 optical microscopy (e.g. Sorby, 1853, 1856; Dieterich, 1969; Siddans, 1972; Wood, 1974;
42 Means, 1981; Weber, 1981) and later with electron microscopy (e.g. Oertel and Phakey, 1972;
43 Oertel et al., 1973; Knipe and White, 1977; White and Knipe, 1978), conventional X-ray pole-
44 figure goniometry (e.g. Oertel, 1983) and electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD; e.g.
45 Cárdenes et al., 2021).

46 In the review we investigated mineral CPOs in randomly selected slate samples with high
47 energy synchrotron X-ray diffraction and observed that extremely high CPO is not unique to
48 Ardennes slates but similar textures are observed in a wide range of geological settings. While
49 phyllosilicates display extreme CPO, surprisingly most quartz CPO, in spite of highly flattened
50 oriented grains (shape preferred orientation, SPO), is practically random. Slates transformed
51 from shales that underwent metamorphism and recrystallization. In shales cleavage is parallel to
52 the bedding plane formed during sedimentation and compaction. The slaty cleavage
53 characteristic of slates is a secondary, tectonic fabric developing at low-grade metamorphic
54 conditions in argillaceous rocks. It reflects the finite strain that these rocks have undergone (e.g.
55 Siddans, 1972; Wood, 1974; Williams, 1977 for overviews). The slaty cleavage primarily
56 represents a compressive strain, with the platelets oriented perpendicular to the principal
57 shortening direction.

58 In our previous studies we have optimized and standardized experimental techniques and
59 methods of data analysis. It turns out that classical methods such as X-ray pole-figure
60 goniometry provide only qualitative information about crystal preferred orientation in slates.
61 Comparatively, with synchrotron diffraction methods the true alignment of phyllosilicates is 5-10
62 times higher. Other techniques like EBSD tends to underestimate phyllosilicate contents, leading
63 to a biased quantification of texture (e.g. Cárdenes et al., 2021). This inspired us to conduct a
64 systematic study of slate textures using synchrotron diffraction, focusing on slates from the
65 Iberian Peninsula which have gained the reputation to represent currently the most important
66 place in the world for industrially produced slates (Cárdenes et al., 2019) and very little is known
67 about their microstructure and texture.

68 The strong CPO of phyllosilicates in low-grade metasediments is typically the result of
69 regional deformation and could define a pervasive foliation over tens and hundreds of kilometers
70 in orogenic belts (e.g. Wood and Oertel, 1980; Pérez-Estaún, et al. 1991; Goldstein et al., 1998;
71 van Norden et al., 2007; Turnbull et al., 2010; Herbolch et al., 2020). This is also expressed in
72 strong anisotropy of elastic properties which, in many cases, is significant for interpreting
73 seismic anisotropy in the crust (e.g. Christensen and Mooney, 1965; Brocher and Christensen,
74 1990; Godfrey et al., 2000; Guo et al., 2014; Ji et al., 2015). Anisotropy is not only expressed in
75 elastic properties but also in the magnetic signature (Haerinck et al., 2015).

76 So far there have been no studies to document the individual influences of both crystal
77 orientation and grain shape on elastic properties. Slates and phyllites with elastically highly
78 anisotropic phyllosilicate crystals provide a unique opportunity to investigate the influence of
79 anisotropic shapes and strong preferred orientation on seismic anisotropy.

80

81 **1. Geological context and sample locations**

82 In this study we have investigated low grade metasediments, slates and phyllites, from three
83 different areas of the Variscan belt in the Iberian Massif.

84 The Variscan orogen developed during the collision of Gondwana and Laurasia in the
85 Paleozoic between 370 and 290 M.a. (Azor et al., 2019). The geology of the Iberian Massif is
86 characterized by an autochthonous Gondwanan domain overlain by an allochthon, which
87 consists of a stack of peri-Gondwanan terranes and ophiolites (Gómez Barreiro et al., 2007).

88 Figure 1a depicts the zonation of the Variscan Iberian Massif. Allochthon and parautochthon are
89 included in the Galicia-Tras-os-Montes Zone (GTMZ) which represents the most internal part of
90 the orogen. It is surrounded by the Central Iberian Zone (CIZ), the eastern portion of which, the
91 Ollo de Sampo Domain, is underlain by the West Asturian-Leonese Zone (WALZ) and the
92 Cantabrian Zone (CZ), both of which represent the Variscan foreland (Julivert et al., 1972;
93 Martínez Catalán et al., 2014).

94 The structural evolution across the Iberian Massif includes contractional (C) and extensional
95 (E) pulses related to plate convergence and gravitational re-equilibration, respectively. The first
96 contractional events produced overturned and recumbent folds (phase C1) followed by the
97 development of major thrusts (C2) and resulted in crustal thickening, which, eventually, led to
98 extensional collapse (E1 and E2) and the formation of gneissic domes through the accumulation
99 of ductile migmatites (Gómez Barreiro et al., 2010; Martínez Catalán et al., 2014). A late-
100 orogenic stage of vertical folding is also recognized (C3; Azor et al., 2019).

101 Here eleven slates and one phyllite from the Upper Proterozoic-Lower Cambrian Schist
102 Greywacke Complex Domain (CIZ), the Lower Cambrian Mondoñedo Nappe Domain (WALZ)
103 and the Lower Cambrian, and Middle-Upper Ordovician Ollo de Sapo Domain (CIZ) have been
104 investigated (Fig. 1a, Table 1 and for sample locations Supplementary Table S1). Samples were
105 not oriented geographically and coordinates used in the text refer to normal of the foliation-
106 cleavage (Z) and lineation (X) visible on hand-specimens. In addition to age, there are
107 differences in the structural and petrological context and metamorphic grade, which will be
108 discussed below. Regional field evidence indicates that our samples are representative of low-
109 grade metapelites from each geological domain over many kilometers, showing thousands of
110 meters in thickness (e.g. Pérez-Estaún et al., 1991; Díez Balda et al., 1990), Those volumes are
111 relevant in terms of seismic exploration (e.g. Godfrey et al., 2000) and our results could be
112 applied to seismic surveys in the Iberian Massif (e.g. Palomeras et al., 2021).

113

114 *1.1. Upper Proterozoic-Lower Cambrian - The Schist-Greywacke Complex (CIZ)*

115 The sample Sa1 (Table 1) was collected from the Schist-Greywacke Complex (SGC) in
116 Salvatierra de Tórmes (Salamanca) in the CIZ (Suppl. Fig. 1). It belongs to the lower section of
117 the SGC in this area, the Monterrubio Formation, which consists of more than 2000 m of

118 metapelites with thin interbedded layers of sandstones, vulcanites and conglomerates (Díez
119 Balda et al., 1990). Original shales were deposited in a slope-distributary channel complex in the
120 context of the Iapetus ocean (Ugidos et al., 2020). Shale metamorphic transformation into a
121 phyllite occurred during the Variscan Orogeny. Several tectono-metamorphic major events in the
122 SGC region have been identified. They can be divided into contractional (C) and extensional (E)
123 phases (Martínez Catalán et al., 2014): C1, generated NNW-SSE subvertical folds with local
124 tectonic foliation (S1); C2, thrusting, which is not present in the area; C3, open to close vertical
125 folds from WNW-ESE to NW-SE trend and a penetrative cleavage (S3). C1 to C3 phases led to a
126 Barrovian metamorphism (360-320 M.a.) with peak conditions $P= 4-5.5$ kbar and $T>650$ °C
127 (Díez Balda et al., 1995; Azor et al., 2019). A subhorizontal extensional shear zone, deformation
128 phase E2, led to a condensation of the Barrovian isogrades and the development of subhorizontal
129 foliation (SE2) which overprinted previous structures below the almandine zone. A gneissic
130 dome is formed during the E2 phase.

131 The sample Sa1 is a phyllite and was collected between the biotite and almandine Barrovian
132 isogrades (<450 °C). The sample shows a penetrative S3 crenulation cleavage, with microlithon
133 domains (Passchier and Trouw, 2005). An open crenulation is visible at different scales (Fig. 2a),
134 being regionally related to the late extensional deformation phase.

135 *1.2. Lower Cambrian - Mondoñedo Nappe Domain (WALZ)*

136 The sample Lugo1 comes from the Cándana Slates (Lower Cambrian; Terra Chá-Lorixe
137 quarry). The area is part of the Mondoñedo Nappe Domain in the WALZ. The Cándana Slates in
138 this area have a thickness of 500 m, with slates, schists and carbonates. The sample Lugo1, a
139 perfect roofing slate, comes from the upper section with ca. 200 m of green to greenish-gray
140 slates (Fig. 3a). The original sediments of the Cándana Group were deposited under shallow
141 marine (littoral) conditions in the Iapetus ocean (Corduban-Ovetian ages; Liñán et al., 2002).
142 Variscan regional metamorphism transformed the original shales into slates and phyllites. The
143 mineral assemblage includes quartz, muscovite, clinocllore and minor biotite (González Lodeiro
144 et al., 1979; Cárdenes et al., 2013). The structure in the area is complex, including regional
145 overturned and recumbent N-S folds (Variscan C1) with axial planar foliation (S1, dated between
146 300 and 335 M.a.; Dallmeyer et al., 1997), which dominates the fabric (Suppl. Fig. 2), and
147 relatively open C3 upright folds with a similar trend, and very local development of cleavage,
148 resulting in cartographic interference patterns (González Lodeiro et al., 1979; Martínez Catalán

149 et al., 2014). The fissility grade of this slate is relatively low (Cárdenes et al., 2013). Variscan
150 deformation led to a Barrovian regional metamorphism. The sample Lugo1 is from within the
151 biotite metamorphic zone (<450 °C).

152 The sample comes from the hinge zone of an overturned C1 fold (Suppl. Fig. 2b). It only
153 shows a penetrative slaty cleavage (S1; dashed lines, Suppl. Fig. 2b), recognized both in hand-
154 sample and outcrop scale. There are no relics of bedding plane (S0) and no trace of late
155 crenulation fabrics (C3) (Fig. 5k). It has the highest content of quartz of all the samples that were
156 analyzed (42.9%, Table 2).

157

158 *1.3. Middle-Upper Ordovician - Ollo de Sapo Domain (CIZ)*

159 Nine samples were collected in the Truchas syncline area (Fig. 1b) of the Ollo de Sapo
160 Domain in the CIZ (Fig. 1a). This is one of the most important areas for roofing slate production
161 in the world with a production of more than 20,000 T/year (Cárdenes et al., 2014). The extraction
162 of roofing slates requires the identification of homogeneous and large volumes, minimizing the
163 presence of secondary foliations, crenulations, veins and fractures which reduce slate fissility
164 (Cardenes et al., 2014). As an aerial overview demonstrates (Suppl. Fig. 3), there are a
165 surprisingly high number of roofing slates quarries, what makes this area a world-class lithotech
166 (Cárdenes et al., 2019).

167 Figure 1b is a simplified geological map of the area with a geological cross section in Figure
168 1c. From a regional perspective, the Truchas syncline is located in the CIZ (Fig. 1b). It is a
169 Variscan synclinorium (Martínez Catalán et al., 1992) formed by several recumbent folds during
170 the first contractional phase (C1). The structure was refolded during the last contractional stage
171 (C3) (Martínez Catalán et al., 2014; Azor et al., 2019). The development of a penetrative slaty
172 cleavage (S1), parallel to the C1 axial planes is widespread all across the syncline (Fig. 1c).
173 Regional metamorphism in the Truchas syncline is low-grade, being related to the Variscan
174 deformation. Mineral assemblages in all samples are in line with previous petrological and
175 crystallinity analyses (e.g. Barros Lorenzo, 1989; Ward and Gómez Fernández, 2003; Cárdenes
176 et al., 2014), indicating low greenschists facies conditions (chlorite zone; 300-400°C; García-
177 Guinea et al., 1997).

178 Samples were collected in different quarries of representative Middle and Upper Ordovician

179 slates (Table 1), corresponding to Luarca and Rozadáis Formations (Fm.) (Fig. 1b). In all cases,
180 samples come from normal limbs of recumbent folds (e.g. Fig.4) and a penetrative slaty cleavage
181 (S1) dominates the fabric. Bedding (S0) is recognized at outcrop scale, defined by silty beds. The
182 angle between S1 and S0 planes ranges between 0-10°, except for Fo8 with 20° (Fig. 2c). The
183 intersection of S0 and S1 planes results into a lineation which has been used as a reference (e.g.
184 Fig. 3c).

185 Sample Piv1 (Figs. 3b and 5j) is a very homogeneous black slate with a perfect slaty
186 cleavage and quartz+feldspar content of 31.7% (Table 2), which comes from the Luarca Fm.
187 (Barrois, 1882). This formation is a monotonous stratigraphic succession of black/gray lutitic
188 slates depending on the organic matter content, with sporadic sandy interlays (cm-dm) and some
189 volcanic rocks on top (Barros Lorenzo, 1989). These shales were deposited during the Oretanian
190 (*ca.* 470-457 M.a.) in a graben basin along the Northern Gondwana continental margin, under
191 anoxic to euxinic conditions (Martínez Catalán et al., 1992; Aramburu and García Ramos, 1993).
192 They were transformed into slates during the Variscan orogeny.

193 The Casaio, Rozadáis and Losadilla Formations represent the Upper Ordovician in the
194 Truchas syncline, consisting of slates, sandstones and quartzites (Fig. 1c). We have sampled
195 different levels of the Rozadáis Fm. This is a slaty sequence with dark-grey and black slates
196 (lower section) evolving into silty slates with interlayered sandstones, quartzites and diamictites
197 (upper section) (Gutiérrez Marco et al., 2002). The highest quality roofing slates comes from the
198 lower section. All samples have a perfect slaty cleavage (S1) and identical structural position
199 (Fig. 3), but slightly different compositions (Table 2). Sample Fo3 is a homogeneous black slate
200 with the lowest quartz + albite content (0.1%; Table 2). Samples Heb1, Fo4, Fo9 are typical
201 black slates with a visible lineation (L1) and a diffuse light-grey banding defining the S0 (e.g.
202 Fig. 3c), their quartz + albite content is <35% (Table 2). Samples Fo2, Fo7 and Fo8 range from
203 black to dark-grey slates, with quartz + albite content varying from 36 to 43% (Table 2). We
204 have selected one sample from the upper section of the Rozadáis Formation favoring mica-rich
205 levels. The Bv5b sample is a black slate with a perfect slaty cleavage (S1) and a visible lineation
206 (L1). The quartz + albite content is 31% (Table 2).

207

208 **2. Microstructures and mineral composition investigated with SEM**

209 Because of the small grain size optical microscopy does not provide much information on the
210 selected samples. Therefore, microstructures were analyzed with scanning electron microscopy
211 (SEM). Samples were cut perpendicular to the cleavage plane (XY) and the lineation (X),
212 polished and carbon-coated and then analyzed with a Zeiss-EVO scanning electron microscope
213 in high vacuum mode, using backscatter (BS) detectors. With BS detectors, the brightness of
214 each phase imaged is dominantly related to their respective atomic numbers, making it easy to
215 identify the main components in our samples: chlorite (bright), muscovite (light grey) and quartz
216 (darker grey). Higher magnifications reveal accessory minerals (<10 Vol%) such as albite (Ab),
217 apatite (Ap), biotite (Bi), ilmenite (Il), monazite (Mo), rutile (R) and pyrite (P) which were
218 identified based on chemical composition with energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). A full list
219 of accessories identified by SEM-EDS analysis can be found in Table 2.

220 In the SEM images of Figure 5 and 6 the cleavage is more or less horizontal, expressed in all
221 but Sa1 by a simple pattern of phyllosilicate platelets aligned parallel to the cleavage. Grain
222 alignment is most regular in Bv5b, Fo3, Fo4, Piv1 and Lugo1.

223 The aspect ratios of the phyllosilicates average to 1:10, but are slightly less for Fo2 and Fo7.
224 Grain size is largest for Bv5b (~20 μm long, Fig. 5a) and smallest for Piv1 (10 μm long, Fig. 5j).
225 While most phyllosilicates are horizontally aligned, there are some exceptions of chlorite-white
226 mica stacks that are oriented oblique to the cleavage direction (e.g. Fo4 Fig. 5e; Piv1 Fig. 5j; Fo3
227 Fig. 6a; Heb1 Fig. 6e).

228 Fo9 shows occasional kink bands (Fig. 5i). The phyllite Sa1 from Salvatierra de Tormes
229 shows a more complex microstructure with clear crenulation cleavage (Fig. 5l and Fig. 6f). The
230 macroscopic foliation corresponds to a crenulation cleavage (S3, red lines in Fig. 6g). Two
231 domains are recognized (Fig. 6h): the cleavage domains, defined by the preferred alignment of
232 muscovite and chlorite, and the quartz-rich microlithons domains, where relics of an older
233 foliation (S1 cleavage) appear transposed (blue lines in Fig. 6 g,h). Note a crenulation (yellow
234 axial lines; Fig 6g) is developed superposed over S3, resulting in a macroscopic crenulation
235 lineation (Fig. 2a). This late feature is tentatively correlated with an extensional stage (SE2). In
236 spite of the complex microstructure, the fissility of Sa1 is good enough to produce thick tiles.

237 Quartz grains are flattened in most samples with an aspect ratio ~ 1:5 (Fig. 5). Sample Fo3
238 has practically no quartz (0.1%, Table 2). Large aggregates of chlorite and chlorite-muscovite

239 stacks (Kisch, 1991) are identified in most of the samples (Figs. 5 and 6), with their basal planes
240 oriented at a high angle to the slaty cleavage (S1) and an aspect ratio of $\sim 1:3$.

241 SEM images clearly display accessories, many with high brightness. Apatite has a prismatic
242 shape and the prisms are more or less aligned parallel to the cleavage plane (Fig. 5d,f). In some
243 samples there are large crystals of monazite showing late-kinematic relationships (e.g. Fo3 Fig.
244 5d; Fo8a Fig. 5g; Fo9 Fig. 6c). In Lugo1 there are large secondary crystals of ilmenite (Fig. 6d).
245 Only in Sa1 could we identify crystals of biotite (Fig. 5l, 6f). They are not platy and appear
246 growing over the microlithons domains, representing a syn/late-S3 phase.

247

248 **3. Crystal preferred orientation measured with synchrotron diffraction**

249 Crystal preferred orientation of fine-grained slates can be measured quantitatively with X-ray
250 diffraction on bulk samples and electron backscatter diffraction on single grains with scanning
251 electron microscopy. Examples of the two methods were discussed in the review and compared
252 with earlier qualitative results from X-ray pole-figure goniometry (Wenk et al., 2020). Here we
253 use high energy synchrotron X-rays because it is an excellent method to quantify high preferred
254 orientation in fine-grained materials. All samples were prepared identically, measured with the
255 same instrumental settings and diffraction data were analyzed with the same methods.

256 After SEM characterization, rectangular prismatic blocks 3-5 mm wide were cut with a
257 diamond saw using the sample XYZ reference system, where Z-axis is perpendicular to the
258 cleavage plane, and X-axis is parallel to the lineation. Then prism edges were grinded down
259 manually to form a cylindrical shape with its axis perpendicular to the cleavage plane (XY) of
260 the sample. This method was better than using a core-drill, which caused fracturing on the
261 cleavage. The cylinders were then mounted on a metal rod and measured at the high energy
262 beamline 11-ID-C of the Advanced Photon Source synchrotron at Argonne National Laboratory.

263 A schematic of the experiment is shown in Figure 7. An X-ray beam with a wavelength of
264 0.1173 \AA (105.7 keV) and a size of $\sim 0.8 \text{ mm} \times 0.8 \text{ mm}$ reaches the sample, which is mounted on
265 a goniometer head with a horizontal rotation axis (Z). The sample is tilted and translated on the
266 goniometer head to bring the center of the cylinder into the center of the beam. About 10 cm
267 behind the sample the primary beam is captured by a beam stop. The diffraction patterns are
268 recorded with a Perkin Elmer 2D image plate detector mounted $\approx 195 \text{ cm}$ from the sample.

269 The experiment takes advantage of the high energy of X-rays, not only for good sample
270 penetration, but also for low diffraction angles (a range of $2\Theta = 0.4\text{--}3.5^\circ$ was used,
271 corresponding to d-spacings 15.0 to 1.92 Å). Recorded diffraction peaks correspond to lattice
272 planes that are barely tilted relative to the incoming X-ray ($\Theta = 0.2\text{--}1.75^\circ$). In the schematic
273 **Figure 12** a much larger wavelength and corresponding large 2Θ is assumed.

274 Before measuring slate samples, the instrument geometry is calibrated with a LaB₆ standard
275 ($a=4.156468$ Å), to refine sample-detector distance, exact detector orientation and instrumental
276 resolution (Caglioti function, Caglioti et al., 1958).

277 Samples were then measured over a ϕ 0–180° rotation range. During measurements, 12
278 composite images at $\phi=15^\circ$ rotation intervals were acquired; each composite image averaged
279 over ~200 images captured using 0.5 s exposure during the rotation interval. The exposure time
280 and number of images per rotation interval has to be adjusted for different sample types to avoid
281 detector saturation. During each rotation interval, the sample was slightly translated along the
282 cylindrical axis (Z) to improve grain statistics. The measurement of a single cylinder, with
283 mounting of the sample, software control, ϕ -rotations and exposure time, takes about 20 minutes.

284 Two typical diffraction patterns for slates Fo3 and Fo4 are shown in Figure 8. Azimuthal
285 intensity variations along η indicate strong preferred orientation for muscovite and chlorite and
286 minimal preferred orientation for quartz, the main mineral constituents in the sample Fo4 (Fig.
287 8b). Fo3 is exceptional, with almost no quartz (Fig. 8a). (00 l) diffractions of phyllosilicates are
288 strongest perpendicular to the vertical cleavage (**vertical** direction in Fig. 8).

289 The 12 images at different ϕ -rotations in 15° intervals (from 0° to 165°) provide an excellent
290 pole-figure coverage for preferred orientation (insert in upper left of Fig. 7). The rotation is about
291 the sample normal to the cleavage plane, which should produce a strong (001) maximum in the
292 center of the phyllosilicate pole-figure.

293 The 12 digital X-ray diffraction images for a single sample were then analyzed
294 simultaneously with the Rietveld method (Rietveld, 1969), which relies on a least-squares fit of a
295 model with measured diffraction information to minimize the difference between experimental
296 diffraction data and a calculated model based on diffractometer parameters, beam intensity,
297 scattering background, crystal structures, preferred orientations and volume fractions of
298 components. For the Rietveld refinement the software MAUD was used (Lutterotti et al., 1997).

299 Details on the software and routine analysis procedures are described in tutorials (Lutterotti et
300 al., 2014; Wenk et al., 2014). First 2D images (Fig. 8) were integrated over 5° azimuthal sectors
301 along the η angle to produce 72 conventional diffraction patterns. A total of $12 \times 72 = 864$ patterns
302 for each sample, with 2θ ranging from 0.4° to 3.5°, were then used in the Rietveld refinement.

303 A polynomial function with five coefficients was used to refine the background of each
304 image and 3-5 minerals were considered depending on sample composition, with corresponding
305 crystallographic information from the literature: 2M-muscovite (Guggenheim et al., 1987, C2/c
306 amcsd 0001076), quartz (Antao et al., 2008, P3₁2₁ amcsd 0006212), and triclinic chlorite
307 (Zanazzi et al., 2009, C-1 amcsd 0007298). We have also tried monoclinic chlorite but the
308 MAUD fit was worse. Other minor phases such as biotite (Bohlen et al., 1980, C2/c amcsd
309 0000756), low albite (Winter et al., 1979, 25C, amcsd 0000715) and apatite (Hughes et al., 1989,
310 P6 3/m amcsd 0001259) were included for some samples. Note that for the texture analysis in
311 MAUD, the first-setting for monoclinic crystals such as muscovite and biotite needs to be
312 applied, i.e. (100) is the cleavage plane instead of the more familiar second-setting with (001) as
313 the cleavage plane (Matthies and Wenk, 2009). But for labels of lattice planes hkl in text, tables
314 and figures we use the more conventional second setting.

315 A comparison of the calculated model (Fig. 9 top) with experimental patterns (Fig. 9 bottom)
316 for sample Fo3 shows a close similarity, indicative of an excellent fit, both in positions as well as
317 intensities of diffraction peaks. Parameters that were refined in the Rietveld analysis were
318 background, lattice parameters of phases, size and shape of crystallites and microstrains (using
319 the anisotropic Popa, 1998 model) as well as volume fractions of phases. Most important for this
320 study are crystallographic preferred orientation distribution functions (ODF) which were refined
321 with the discrete EWIMV method, based on WIMV (Matthies and Vinel, 1982, Wenk et al.,
322 2003; Lutterotti et al., 2004) but allowing for arbitrary data coverage. No sample symmetry was
323 imposed and an ODF 7.5° cell size was considered for the discrete orientation space for every
324 mineral. The ODF was then exported from MAUD and introduced into the BEARTEX software
325 (Wenk et al., 1998) to rotate the sample orientation such that the center of the pole-figure is the
326 normal to the cleavage plane (Z-axis) and, if there is a girdle-like distribution, the girdle is
327 vertical, i.e. normal to the lineation. The transformed ODFs were then used to calculate and plot
328 pole-figures of minerals as well as to model bulk elastic properties of each sample.

329 The main phases in all samples are white mica, chlorite and quartz (Table 2). Quartz ranges
330 from 0-43 Vol%. Muscovite is the dominant phyllosilicate (35-64 Vol%) and chlorite ranges
331 from 16-36 Vol%. Based on refined lattice parameters and EDS analyses, muscovite in all
332 samples is basically pure $\text{KAl}_2[\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10}(\text{OH})_2]$ (Supplementary Table S2). There is some
333 variation for chlorite but it is compositionally close to
334 $(\text{Mg,Fe})_3(\text{OH})_6(\text{Mg,Fe})_2\text{Al}[\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10}(\text{OH})_2]$, with an approximate 1:3 Mg:Fe ratio
335 (Supplementary Table S4). Note that our EDS analyses are semi-quantitative and should not be
336 used to calculate mineral formulae. Supplementary Tables S3 and S5 list refined lattice
337 parameters.

338 The main focus of this study has been CPOs. Orientation distribution functions (ODFs), as
339 well as pole density values are expressed in multiples of random distribution (mrd) with 1 mrd
340 corresponding to an isotropic distribution (or absence of preferred orientation) and ∞
341 corresponding to a single crystal. Pole-figures are displayed for muscovite (Fig. 10), chlorite
342 (Fig. 11), quartz (Fig. 12), apatite (Fig. 13a) and biotite (Fig. 13b). Some information is
343 summarized in Table 3. Pole-figures are projected on the cleavage plane (XY) to produce
344 minimal distortion of the dominant (001) maximum (in the center) and display deviations from
345 axial symmetry. In the orthogonal coordinate system Z is the normal to the cleavage plane, X is
346 the lineation direction and Y perpendicular to it (Figs. 10-13).

347 For muscovite the (001) pole-figure maxima vary from 25 mrd to 120 mrd, for chlorite from
348 13 mrd to 125 mrd. The strongest preferred orientations are in Lugo1 (muscovite 120 mrd and
349 chlorite 125 mrd) and Fo4 (muscovite 83 mrd, chlorite 84 mrd), and relatively weak orientations
350 were observed in Fo2 (muscovite 25 mrd, chlorite 22 mrd), Fo8 (muscovite 29 mrd, chlorite 37
351 mrd) and Sa1 (muscovite 42 mrd, chlorite 14 mrd). In many samples muscovite and chlorite
352 show similar maxima, an exception is Sa1 where chlorite is much weaker. All samples show a
353 girdle in the YZ plane, most pronounced in Fo8, Fo9, Lugo and Sa1. In Fo3 and Piv1 the
354 distributions are close to axial symmetry. Texture patterns for Sa1 reflect the crenulation
355 cleavage, with a minor (001) sub-maximum in Y (both for chlorite and muscovite), which
356 correlates with S1 planes in Figure 6h.

357 In actual 3D orientation distributions (ODF) exported from MAUD, ODF maxima are
358 considerably higher than (001) pole-figure maxima (Table 3) reaching 310 mrd for muscovite

359 and 951 mrd for chlorite in Lugo1. This is due to the fact that pole-figures are normalized
360 integral ODF projections.

361 Perhaps most surprising has been the effective absence of significant preferred orientation for
362 quartz (Fig. 12) in spite of the highly flattened grain shape as displayed in SEM images (Fig. 5).
363 Except for phyllite Sa1 with fairly equiaxed quartz, aspect ratios range from 1:4 to 1:8. Pole-
364 figure maxima for quartz range from 1.3 mrd to 2.3 mrd. Pole density values of <1.4 mrd are
365 most likely artifacts of the Rietveld analysis with extremely oriented phyllosilicates and
366 diffraction peaks overlapping with quartz. The highest CPO with a (0001) maximum of 2.3 mrd
367 was observed in Sa1 (with a weak phyllosilicate texture and equiaxed quartz grains) but the pole-
368 figure does not correspond to any typical textures documented in quartzites where quartz (0001)
369 CPO generally exceeds 5 mrd, with regular patterns (e.g. Menegon et al., 2008; Pehl and Wenk,
370 2005; Toy et al., 2008; Wenk et al., 2019). There appears to be a slight tendency for a
371 concentration of poles of positive rhombs perpendicular to the cleavage plane, which could be
372 attributed to mechanical Dauphiné twinning (e.g. Minor et al., 2018). But this is questionable
373 because the strong quartz (10-11) diffraction peak overlies with the strong muscovite (006) peak
374 (Fig. 8b).

375 We have explored orientation patterns of some accessories. Albite does not display any
376 coherent orientation. Prismatic apatite in Fo3 aligns with [0001] preferentially in the lineation
377 direction X (Fig. 13a), which is comparable with SEM microstructures (Fig. 5b). Biotite in Sa1
378 displays a weak preferred orientation of (001) (3 mrd) with submaxima at 30° to the foliation
379 plane (Z-axis) that is consistent with its microstructural position and the patterns for muscovite
380 and chlorite (Fig. 13b).

381

382 **4. Elastic anisotropy based on crystal and shape preferred orientation**

383 Elastic properties are needed to determine seismic velocities, and particularly their
384 anisotropy. Slates, composed of elastically highly anisotropic muscovite and chlorite with strong
385 alignment are significant contributors to seismic anisotropy in the crust (e.g. Guo et al., 2014;
386 Cárdenes et al., 2021). These slate samples with extraordinary textures provide an excellent case
387 to explore the influence of mineral composition, crystal and shape preferred orientation on
388 seismic anisotropy and elastic properties of polymineralic rocks. While there are lots of data on

389 anisotropy of shales (e.g. Hornby 1998), there is very little information about low grade
390 metasediments, in particular slates which are an important component of the continental crust in
391 many orogenic belts (e.g. Christensen and Mooney, 1965; Godfrey et al., 2000). We start with a
392 brief survey on how crystal and shape preferred orientation can be used to calculate elastic
393 properties.

394 Linear elastic properties of a material are described with the twice-symmetric fourth-rank
395 stiffness tensor C_{ijkl} (or compliance S_{ijkl} , which satisfies the “inversion relation” $C_{ijkl} \equiv S_{ijkl}^{-1}$) that,
396 in the general case, has 21 independent components (e.g., Nye, 1985). If single crystal properties
397 0C or 0S are known, elastic properties of a textured polycrystal can be estimated averaging over
398 the ODFs $f(g)$. In the simplest form this can be written as an arithmetic average of stiffness over
399 all crystals (Voigt average, Voigt, 1887) or an average of compliance (Reuss average, Reuss,
400 1929). Both averages allow for calculation of properties of multiphase polycrystals by including
401 volume fractions of different phases. A Voigt average is higher (upper bound of the polycrystal
402 properties) than the Reuss average (lower bound). The real elastic properties of the polycrystal
403 are between the two. Different methods were proposed to narrow these bounds, e.g., using an
404 arithmetic mean of Voigt and Reuss results (Hill, 1952), or geometric mean models (Matthies
405 and Humbert, 1995). The latter additionally obey the statistically important group principle
406 (Matthies et al., 2001).

407 Such relatively simple methods consider only ODFs, volume fractions and single crystal
408 elastic properties of constituent phases, and disregard details of grain interactions, or grain
409 shapes. Microstructural peculiarities, stress equilibrium and strain compatibility between grains
410 may be correctly addressed with finite element methods, yet these are rarely applied to such
411 complex anisotropic and heterogeneous materials as multiphase rocks. They require a great
412 amount of experimental information on rock microstructure, and therefore applications are
413 mostly limited to studies of isotropic rocks or 2D cases (e.g., Makarynska et al., 2008; Zhong et
414 al., 2014; Srisutthiyakorn et al., 2018).

415 Another approach is to use an iterative self-consistent algorithm that calculates elastic
416 properties of the polycrystal, treating it as an effective medium composed of grains approximated
417 by ellipsoidal inclusions (e.g., Kröner, 1958; Morris, 1970, Fig. 14). To model bulk elastic
418 coefficients of slates we use a modified self-consistent method GeoMIXself (GMS) (Matthies,
419 2010, 2012) that adds elements of the geometric mean model (Matthies and Humbert, 1995) to

420 conventional self-consistent routines to produce a unique solution for elastic properties exactly
421 obeying the inversion relation. As an effective medium approach, GMS neglects correlations in
422 positions of grains, and thus requires only ‘global’ orientation distributions. CPO’s are readily
423 obtained from a diffraction experiment as described above. Shape orientation distributions (SPO)
424 may be either derived from CPO’s considering additional rotations when the grain shape is
425 related to crystallographic cleavage planes as in phyllosilicates (Vasin et al., 2013), or be
426 represented as δ -function in the sample coordinate system if grain shapes are defined by a
427 macroscopic deformation process, as in case of highly flattened quartz grain shapes in the
428 studied slates.

429 Volume fractions of minerals are available from the Rietveld refinement (Table 2), and single
430 crystal elastic constants of minerals are taken from the literature. We use elastic tensors
431 measured by Vaughan and Guggenheim (1986) for muscovite (the latter has to be changed to
432 first monoclinic setting to comply with the CPO analysis) and by Heyliger et al. (2003) for
433 quartz. The stiffness tensor of chlorite has been estimated by measurements (Alexandrov and
434 Rhyzhova, 1961) and more recently by first principles calculations (Mookherjee and Mainprice,
435 2014; Ulian et al., 2018). Here we use results from Mookherjee and Mainprice (2014) assuming
436 a monoclinic unit cell. In slates, triclinic chlorite is present, but two lattice angles are close to
437 right angles; thus for calculations we used the monoclinic tensor taking into account that it is
438 provided in a coordinate system related to stacking crystal planes and therefore to the grain
439 shape.

440 Let us demonstrate first the single crystal elastic anisotropies of the three mineral phases that
441 compose most of slates. Using mineral stiffnesses and densities, elastic wave velocities have
442 been calculated with BEARTEX. Figure 15 displays longitudinal P-velocity distributions,
443 projected on the cleavage plane for muscovite and chlorite, and on (0001) plane for quartz.
444 Elastic anisotropy can be qualitatively described using V_P values as $An\% = 200(V_{Pmax} -$
445 $V_{Pmin}) / (V_{Pmax} + V_{Pmin})$. Clearly muscovite has the highest elastic anisotropy of 56.4%. Chlorite has
446 a much weaker anisotropy of 30.0%, which Ulian et al. (2018) attribute to distortions of the
447 interlayer due to Al and Fe. Anisotropy of quartz is even weaker – 25.9%.

448 Aspect ratios of mineral grains in slates were assessed from SEM images (Figs. 5, 6).
449 Evidently, there is a distribution of shapes. To use shapes in GMS, for every mineral this
450 distribution has to be represented by a single ellipsoidal shape. Thus, for calculated elastic

451 properties of slates listed in Table 4 for all samples average {1:1:0.1} grain shapes for
452 phyllosilicate and {1:1:0.2} shapes for quartz were used. To investigate the effect of the grain
453 shape on slate elastic properties, we used GMS to model Lugo slate elasticity assuming different
454 phyllosilicate shapes {1:1:0.01}, {1:1:0.1}, {1:1:1}, and quartz shapes {1:1:0.2} and {1:1:1}
455 (Table 5).

456 Results for the GMS averaging are expressed as 21 stiffness coefficients for each slate
457 sample (Table 4, 5). C_{11} coefficients, corresponding to the lination direction X, range from 132
458 to 172 GPa. C_{33} coefficients, the stiffness along the softest direction Z perpendicular to the
459 cleavage range from 77 to 90 GPa. These stiffness coefficients and slate densities computed from
460 mineral densities and refined volume fractions, were then used to calculate elastic wave
461 velocities with BEARTEX. Distributions of P-wave velocities and shear wave splitting
462 (difference between fast and slow shear waves) in slates are shown in Figure 16. In all slates,
463 slowest P-waves are in direction perpendicular to the cleavage plane (Z), corresponding to the
464 preferred orientation of (001) normals of phyllosilicates, and highest shear wave splitting is in
465 the XY plane.

466

467 **5. Discussion**

468 *5.1. Crystal and shape preferred orientation*

469 Preferred orientation patterns for muscovite and chlorite in Spanish slates are similar to those
470 observed in a worldwide survey (Wenk et al., 2020). However, Spanish slates consistently
471 display a girdle-like distribution (Figs. 10, 11). This can be quantified by looking in (001) pole-
472 figures at the angular half-width at 1 mrd in the XZ plane (a) and the YZ plane (b) (Table 3,
473 (001) a-b). For muscovite the sharpest width (a) in XZ is 17° for Lugo1 and ranges from 17° to
474 24°. In the YZ plane (b) the range is much broader, from 32° (Lugo1) to 55° (Fo8a). Fo8 is the
475 sample with the macroscopically well-visible inclined bedding plane (Fig 3c). The difference (b-
476 a) is smallest for Piv1 (9°) with an almost axially symmetric pattern. A similar pattern is
477 observed for chlorite. To quantify this girdle distribution, it is crucial to project pole figures
478 along Z on the cleavage plane (XY) to avoid distortions due to spherical projections. For
479 projections along the lination (X) (001) pole figures of phyllosilicates look distorted, also for
480 axial symmetry (e.g. Cárdenes et al., 2021).

481 The girdle distribution observed in Spanish slates is different from some (001) pole-figures
482 observed in the Belgian Ardennes (Be-E1, E2), Hunsrück-Germany (Sturtz), Brittany-France
483 (Sin2), and the Eastern Sierra Nevada in California (NS3), which are basically axially symmetric
484 (Fig. 19 in Wenk et al., 2020). Samples described here were subjected not only to axial
485 compression but also plane strain, with extension and simple shear in the lineation direction, as
486 demonstrated by the YZ girdle for chlorite and muscovite (001). This is consistent with the
487 structural evolution in this part of the Variscan orogen (Pérez-Estaún et al., 1991; Azor et al.,
488 2019). The sample with the most pronounced crenulation cleavage Sa1 displays the largest YZ
489 spreading of phyllosilicate (001) normals.

490 Microstructures with fairly euhedral platy crystals of muscovite and chlorite, with not much
491 evidence of kinking (e.g. in Fo9, Fig. 5i) or grain boundary sliding, are consistent with
492 recrystallisation under stress (Kamb 1959; Shimizu 1992, 2008), rather than rigid particle
493 rotations that have been proposed by Oertel and Curtis (1972), Oertel (1983) and Sintubin
494 (1994), using the Jeffery (1923) and March (1932) theories. The dominant mechanism appears to
495 be pressure solution and reprecipitation (e.g. Weyl, 1959; Plessmann, 1964, 1966; Durney, 1972;
496 Rutter, 1976; De Boer, 1977; Wright and Platt, 1982; Lee et al., 1986; Ishii, 1988; Kanagawa,
497 1991; Karasawa and Kano, 1992; Ho et al., 2001; Imon et al., 2004) and would also account for
498 flattened quartz grains growing parallel to phyllosilicate platelets in pressure shadows (e.g.
499 Pabst, 1931; Passchier and Trouw, 2005), with random crystal orientations.

500 Fo8a has a pronounced bedding plane at 20° to the cleavage (S1) plane (Fig. 2c), but this
501 does not seem to be expressed significantly in the texture, except for the broadness of the texture
502 band mentioned above (Fig. 10, 11). Measurements on a second sample from the same hand
503 specimen (Fo8b) shows basically the same pattern (Table 3). The bedding plane/cleavage
504 intersection is visible by weak diagonal structures on slate cleavage surfaces (top left/bottom
505 right in Fig. 3). While the bedding plane is obvious in the hand specimen (Fig. 2c), it not well
506 expressed in SEM microstructures, except a weak diagonal stacking of platelets top right/bottom
507 left e.g. in Fo8a (Fig. 5g), Piv1 (Fig. 5j) and Lugo1 (Fig. 5k). One question is the total strain to
508 which slates were subjected. It cannot be very large since inclined bedding planes are observed
509 that would be distorted by large shortening (Fig. 2c). With dissolution and reprecipitation under
510 significant stress at low temperature strong textures may form without significant plastic
511 deformation by dislocation glide, e.g. of quartz.

512 Fo3 is an exceptional slate from the Os Follos quarry. It has no significant quartz content and
513 occurs as thin lens-like layers between regular slates (Fig. 4).

514 The influence of metamorphic grade on slate microstructures has been discussed (e.g.
515 Siddans, 1976; Wood et al., 1976; Knipe, 1979, 1981; Morris, 1981; Lee et al., 1986; Ho et al.,
516 1995; Van Norden et al., 2007; Jacques et al. 2014). In the case of Spanish metasediments
517 studied here, metamorphic grade ranges from lower to upper greenschist facies. Highest grade,
518 with some biotite, applies to Sa1 and Lugo1, which can be classified as phyllites. In all samples
519 microstructures indicate that muscovite and chlorite crystallized in equilibrium with euhedral
520 crystals, only rarely bent and particularly often interlayered at micron-scale (Figs. 5e, j, 6a,e).
521 This interlayering complicates chemical EDS analyses because small amounts of
522 muscovite/chlorite may be included in chlorite/muscovite analyses (Supplementary Tables S3
523 and S5).

524 Mineral composition is quite simple in all samples, with muscovite, Fe-Mg chlorite and
525 quartz as the main phases, and minor components like albite (<10%, Table 2), depicting an
526 overall textural equilibrium under greenschist facies. Typical lepidoblastic microstructure
527 dominates the fabric, which can be easily correlated to regional axial plane foliation in all cases.
528 Only in the case of the highest metamorphic grade (phyllite Sa1) with the presence of biotite and
529 a crenulation cleavage (e.g. Cosgrove, 1976; Gray, 1977; Gray and Durney, 1979; Passchier and
530 Trouw, 2005), related to a late extensional collapse (SE2), there is a relatively complex evolution
531 (Fig. 6). In Sa1, biotite crystals are large but scarce (<5%) and show a syn/late-kinematic
532 character with respect to the principal foliation (S3 cleavage). Also Sa1 is the only sample where
533 quartz does not have a flattened grain shape as a result of the formation process of microlithons
534 domains (Fig. 6h) and displays a significant crystal preferred orientation (Fig. 12). Biotite has a
535 similar girdle-like distribution as muscovite and chlorite (Fig. 13b).

536 Determining lattice parameters of muscovite and chlorite in the Rietveld refinement
537 (Supplementary Tables S2, S4), as well as estimating chemical composition with EDS analyses
538 (Supplementary Tables S3, S5) suggests no systematic variations with metamorphic grade.
539 Muscovite contains no Na. Chlorites have all similar Fe/Mg ratios (~2.5), perhaps slightly lower
540 for high grade Lugo1 and Sa1 (~2.2).

541 There are consistent accessories (<3%) in most samples, apatite, pyrite and rutile (Table 2).
542 Apatite with prismatic shape deformed with phyllosilicates and developed significant texture,
543 with [0001] aligned in the lamination direction (X in Fig. 13a). Monazite has been documented in
544 Fo3, Fo8 and Fo9. Lugo1 contains relatively large phenocrysts of ilmenite (Fig. 6d) that grew
545 and replaced phyllosilicates and quartz. Albite is present in many samples but displays no
546 significant preferred orientation (0-10%, Table 2).

547 Grain size was similar in slates sampled from the same location. On average, phyllosilicates
548 were similarly sized within a sample ranging from 5-20 μm in length and 1-3 μm in width. All
549 Fo samples showed an average of phyllosilicates 10 μm in length and 2 μm in width and quartz
550 around 12 μm in length and 3 μm in width. The largest grains were found in sample Bv5b with
551 phyllosilicates average in length 20 μm and 2 μm in width, and the smallest grains in Piv1 with
552 phyllosilicates average in length 7 μm and 2 μm in width. The average size of quartz across all
553 samples is around 27 μm in length and 5 μm in width.

554 One of the most important properties of slates related to texture is fissility (Cardenes et al.,
555 2014). Splitting into thin slate plates (i.e. 4-10 mm thickness) up to certain dimensions
556 (minimum 32x20cm) is critical to determine the potential of the rock for being a high-quality
557 roofing slate (Fig. 3, e.g. García-Guinea et al., 1998). A homogeneous distribution of grain-sizes
558 is critical for a regular cleavage. Muscovite and chlorite were relatively homogeneously sized
559 within samples, with the exception of chlorite-mica stacks oriented obliquely to the overall fabric
560 (e.g. Fig. 6a, e). However, these larger grains only compose <5% of any sample. Besides, there is
561 a close correlation between mechanical properties of slates and their fabric (e.g. bending
562 strength; Wagner, 2007; Gómez-Fernández et al., 2012). The quartz content is a significant
563 factor modifying both fabric and mechanical response of the slate, affecting its workability and
564 slate hardness (Cárdenes et al., 2014).

565 In our samples quartz shows a strong shape preferred orientation (Fig. 5), but an almost
566 random texture (Fig. 12). Preferred orientation of phyllosilicates is recognized as an important
567 feature to define mechanical strength in slates, but it is poorly defined in test methods and
568 standards (Gómez Fernández et al., 2012). To explore the interlink between mineral composition
569 and phyllosilicates texture we have represented in the Figure 17 the covariance of the (001) pole
570 figure maximum value (mrd) of muscovite and chlorite, and the abundance of tectosilicates in

571 the rock (quartz + albite, Table 2). Our results show that in most samples within the common
572 compositional range for Spanish roofing slates, phyllosilicate texture strength decreases as
573 tectosilicate content increases (Fig. 17). Both muscovite and chlorite display a similar behavior
574 as suggested by microstructural observations (Figs. 5 and 6). Even slates like Fo3, with a very
575 low content of tectosilicates are compatible with this trend. The exception of Lugo1 phyllite
576 could be explained because at relatively higher metamorphic grade texture becomes less
577 dependent on mineral composition.

578 *5.2. Elastic anisotropy*

579 All slates have strong elastic anisotropy as expressed by P- and S-waves calculated based on
580 microstructures and preferred orientation (Table 4, Fig. 16). There is a P-wave velocity minimum
581 perpendicular to the cleavage (in Z direction) and a maximum in the lineation direction (X) with
582 strong shear-wave splitting in the cleavage plane. The P-wave anisotropy coefficient A_n ranges
583 from 19.8% (Sa1) to 39.4% (Fo3). Fo3 is the sample without quartz, almost entirely composed of
584 phyllosilicates. Maximum shear wave splitting in the 11 samples ranges from 0.6 to 1.8 km/s.
585 Fo3 demonstrates maximum splitting due to minimal quartz content.

586 The Spanish slates provide excellent samples to explore the assumptions of different
587 averaging models and particularly the influence of grain shape on anisotropy in a polymineralic
588 rock. They are highlighted in Table 5 for Lugo1,. As was mentioned earlier, the Voigt model
589 provides an upper bound for polycrystal elastic properties with high P-wave velocities, while the
590 Reuss model provides a lower bound with lower velocities. These models may provide very
591 different stiffness coefficient of the rock (e.g., Vasin et al., 2013), but in the case of Lugo1 slate
592 calculated C_{ij} 's are quite close. This is due to sharp textures of the main slate minerals –
593 phyllosilicates. Consequently, GMS models, intermediate between Voigt and Reuss bounds, also
594 provide similar elastic properties. There is not much difference between extremely flat grains of
595 phyllosilicates (aspect ratio of 0.01) and flat grains corresponding best with observed
596 microstructures (0.1). Both models provide high A_n and dS_{max} values. Assuming spherical
597 phyllosilicate grains (1:1:1) results in a 5% lower A_n , as well as lower shear wave splitting.
598 Thus, the sophisticated GMS model improves estimates of elastic anisotropy. Considering
599 random CPO or spherical grain shapes for quartz instead of oriented {1:1:0.2} platelets barely
600 affect slate elastic properties and anisotropy. In this regard, rather low A_n values of $\approx 13.6 \pm 3.0\%$
601 were recently reported for some Spanish slates investigated with EBSD and explored for elastic

602 anisotropy with the Hill model (Cardenes et al., 2021), compared to our results with An 20-40%,
603 Table 4). This could be attributed both to underestimation of phyllosilicate content with EBSD
604 and the simplified arithmetic mean of the Hill approach, which disregards grain shapes.

605 In Table 5 we also compare elastic anisotropy of Lugo1 slate with gneiss and shale. For
606 amphibolite facies Tambo muscovite gneiss modeled and measured elastic properties show much
607 lower anisotropy than slate (Vasin et al., 2017) with 7.5% anisotropy compared with ~28% for
608 slate. This is largely due to the much lower phyllosilicate content (17% muscovite) and lower
609 CPO (10 mrd). For biotite gneiss from the Outokumpu drill hole in Finland with 23% biotite and
610 22 mrd, anisotropy is 16% (Kern et al., 2009; Wenk et al., 2012). This is similar to other studies
611 of gneiss and schists (e.g. Godfrey et al., 2000; Kern et al., 2001; Cholach and Schmitt, 2006;
612 Valcke et al., 2006; Wenk et al., 2010, Fazio et al., 2017).

613 Anisotropy is also stronger in the slates studied here than in shales, even after taking aligned
614 porosity into account, e.g. Kimmeridge shale (Hornby, 1998; Vasin et al., 2013; Vernik and Liu,
615 1997, Table 5), Mont Terri clay (Wenk et al., 2008), Posidonia shale (Kanitpanyacharoen et al.,
616 2012) and experimentally compressed clay mixtures (Voltolini et al., 2009). For Kimmeridge
617 shale with 67% phyllosilicates and illite (001) at 6.7 mrd anisotropy is 22%, including aligned
618 porosity (Vasin et al., 2013).

619 For slates we did not take microfractures into account for calculating elastic properties. Some
620 are revealed by black regions in SEM images (Fig. 5). They do not seem associated with the
621 cleavage plane, are rather equiaxed and may have originated during sample preparation. Oriented
622 fractures have been considered in GMS modeling of shales (e.g. Vasin et al., 2013), gneiss (e.g.
623 Vasin et al., 2017) and Westerley granite (Lokajicek et al., 2020). In case of these slates-oriented
624 fractures do not seem to significantly influence elastic properties, or enhance the elastic
625 anisotropy. On the contrary, low amounts of randomly distributed equiaxed fractures would
626 slightly decrease the slate elastic anisotropy. In the future, ultrasonic velocities in slates should
627 be measured experimentally at different confining pressures to elucidate the effect of
628 microfractures.

629 Shales transforming to slates in metasedimentary basins as in Spain may contribute
630 significantly to observed seismic anisotropy in the crust (e.g. Christensen and Mooney, 1965). In
631 fact, several recent studies document seismic anisotropy in Northern Spain (e.g. Barroul et al.,

632 1998; Diaz et al., 2006; Acevedo et al., 2021), attributing it tentatively to serpentinite, even
633 though anisotropy of slates is much higher and may be very significant for interpreting seismic
634 data. From a regional point of view, in the Iberian Massif, low-grade metasediments show a
635 pervasive tectonic foliation related to the Variscan orogeny deformation in the Paleozoic (Azor
636 et al., 2019). The presence of kilometer-scale volumes of highly anisotropic rocks like slates and
637 phyllites, should be considered to evaluate, for example, the role of the anisotropy on the
638 reflectivity (Blangy, 1994; Godfrey et al., 2000), or the interpretation of the recent findings in
639 seismic experiments in the Iberian Massif (e.g. Diaz et al. 2006; Ruiz et al., 2017; Palomeras et
640 al., 2021).

641 *5.3. Suggestions for future studies*

642 This study on microstructures, preferred orientation and seismic anisotropy adds important
643 new information on these enigmatic rocks but it also opens new questions that should be
644 addressed in the future. While there is a lot of information on shales and slates, there is little
645 information how a shale transforms to a slate. Material from N Spain may provide an opportunity
646 since old shales are available and transformations have been investigated geochemically (e.g.
647 Clauer et al., 2014). This transition should also be investigated experimentally to shed light on
648 the mechanisms of dissolution – reprecipitation at low grade conditions.

649 Another issue is organic matter. “Organic” slates/shales, or argillites have been described in
650 coal deposits, but very little is known about the transition of argillites into slates and
651 corresponding microstructures and textures (e.g. Large et al., 1994; Suarez et al., 2012, Suchy et
652 al., 2007). Slates from the California Shoe Fly Ftn. with a high carbon content display only very
653 weak fabrics. The Middle-Upper Ordovician slates sampled in the Rozadais and Luarca
654 Formations have similar organic matter contents (<0.3%), while the Lower Cambrian and Upper
655 Proterozoic phyllites typically show no trace of organic matter (e.g. Cárdenes et al., 2014,
656 Lombardero et al., 2002). As a consequence, the Ordovician slates depict dark black-grey colors,
657 while the high-grade slates are greenish-grey. The green color of the Cambrian phyllite (Lugo1,
658 Fig. 4a) has been attributed to the presence of clinocllore (Cardenes et al., 2014), although our
659 sample has a similar iron content as the other chlorites (Supplementary Table S4). Lugo1 has the
660 strongest preferred orientation, visible in its regular horizontal alignment of phyllosilicate grains
661 (Fig. 5k).

662 Another issue ready for experimental studies is seismic anisotropy which was so far only
663 approached with measurements at ambient conditions which are subject to an excessive influence
664 of open fractures, as demonstrated in the recent studies of Guo et al. (2014) and Cárdenes et al.
665 (2021). Experiments with state-of-the-art methods such as Kern et al. (2009) and Lokajiczek et
666 al. (2021) would add valuable new information.

667

668 **6. Conclusions**

669 A study of greenschist metamorphic slates from Northern Spain reveals extremely strong
670 preferred orientation of muscovite and chlorite. Fairly euhedral grain shapes suggest formation
671 from original shales by pressure solution and reprecipitation with recrystallization. The high
672 CPO could be quantified with high energy synchrotron X-ray diffraction and Rietveld texture
673 analysis. Results are about an order of magnitude higher than previously documented with
674 conventional methods such as pole-figure goniometry. By contrast quartz, a significant
675 percentage of slate compositions, has also flattened shapes, but random CPO. With increasing
676 quartz content phyllosilicate CPO decreases. The girdle-like distribution of muscovite and
677 chlorite (001) CPO implies that a significant proportion of strain was plane strain, including
678 simple shear. Due to high CPO of phyllosilicates slates display strong elastic anisotropy (20-
679 40%) and since they are important components in tectonic settings around the world, including
680 our sampling locations in Northern Spain, they strongly contribute to observed seismic
681 anisotropy in the crust, which should be incorporated into future seismic models.

682

683 **Credit authorship contribution statement**

684 All authors contributed to experiments, data analysis, writing and reviewing the manuscript.
685 Hans-Rudolf Wenk conceptualized the project, collected samples, performed synchrotron
686 experiments at APS. Jingyi Huang performed the Rietveld data analysis to obtain quantitative
687 texture information. Michelle Devoe was in charge of SEM analyses to reveal microstructures.
688 Juan Gomez-Barreiro wrote the section on geologic setting and collected samples. Yang Ren was
689 in charge of synchrotron diffraction experiments at APS. Santos Barrios-Sanchez contributed to
690 the geologic setting. Roman Vasin was in charge of the modeling of elastic properties.

691

692 Declaration of competing interest

693 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
694 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

695

696 Acknowledgements

697 We acknowledged access to beamline 11-ID-C of the Advanced Photon Source at Argonne
698 National Laboratory and supported by DOE Office of Science under Contract No. DE-AC02-
699 06CH11357 and the Zeiss EVO SEM at EPS, UC Berkeley. HRW is appreciative for support
700 from NSF (EAR 1343908) and DOE-BES (DE-FG02-05ER15637) and from The Fulbright
701 Foundation for a fellowship in Salamanca. JH was supported by the China Scholarship Council
702 and National Key Research and Development Program No. 2016YFC0303902-04. JGB
703 appreciates financial support from MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, PID2020-117332GB-
704 C21. We greatly acknowledge discussions and access to quarries by Victor Cárdenes (Oviedo
705 University) and José Eladio (SAMACA at Valdeorras). John Grimsich at UC Berkeley helped
706 with sample preparation and SEM analyses. Crucial for this study were software packages
707 MAUD developed by Luca Lutterotti and GeoMIXSelf developed by Siegfried Matthies. We are
708 grateful for their help.

709

710 **References**

- 711 Acevedo, J., Fernandez-Viejo, G., Llana-Funez, S., Lopez-Fernandez, C., Olona, J., 2021.
712 Upper-crustal seismic anisotropy in the Cantabrian Mountains (North Spain) from shear-
713 wave splitting and ambient noise interferometry analysis. *Seismol. Res. Letters* 92, 421-436.
- 714 Alexandrov, K. S., Ryzhova, T. V., 1961. Elastic properties of rock-forming minerals. II.
715 Layered silicates. *Bull. Academy Sciences USSR, Geophys. Series* 9, 1165-1168.
- 716 Antao, S. M., Hassan, I., Wang, J., Lee, P. L., Toby, B. H., 2008. State-of-the-art high resolution
717 powder x-ray diffraction (HRPXRD) illustrated with Rietveld structure refinement of quartz,
718 sodalite, tremolite, and meionite. *Canad. Mineral.* 46, 1501-1509.
- 719 Azor, A., Días da Silva, I., Gómez Barreiro, J., González Clavijo, E., Martínez Catalán, J. R.,
720 Simancas, J. F., Martínez Poyato, s D., Pérez Cáceres, s I., González Lodeiro, F., Expósito, I.,
721 Casas, J. M., Clariana, P., García-Sanseguendo, J., Margalef, A., 2019. Deformation and
722 structure. in: Quesada C., Oliveira T. eds: *The Geology of Iberia: A Geodynamic Approach:*
723 *Volume 2: The Variscan Cycle* 307-348 Springer International Publishing DOI 10.1007/978-
724 3-030-10519-8, ISBN: 978-3-030-10518-1.
- 725 Barrois, C., 1882. *Recherches sur les terrains anciens des Asturies et la Galicie.* Soc. Géol. Fr.
726 *Mém.* 2.
- 727 Barruol, G., Souriau, A., Vauchez, A., Díaz, J., Gallart, J., Tubia, J., Cuevas, J.,
728 1998. Lithospheric anisotropy beneath the Pyrenees from shear-wave splitting, *J. Geophys.*
729 *Res.* 103, 30,039–30,053.
- 730 Barros Lorenzo, J. C., 1989. Nuevos datos geológicos y cartográficos sobre el flanco Sur del
731 Sinclinatorio de Truchas. *Cadernos do Laboratorio Xeolóxico de Laxe* 14, 93–116.
- 732 Blangy, J. P., 1994. AVO in transversely isotropic media-An overview. *Geophysics*, 59, 775-781.
733 DOI: 10.1190/1.1443635.
- 734 Bohlen, S.R., Peacor, D.R., Essene, E.J., 1980. Crystal chemistry of a metamorphic biotite and
735 its significance in water barometry. *Am. Mineral.* 65, 55-62.
- 736 Caglioti, G., Paoletti, A., Ricci, F.P., 1958. Choice of collimators for a crystal spectrometer for
737 neutron diffraction. *Nuclear Instruments* 3, 223-228.

- 738 Cárdenes, V., Ponce de León, M., Rodríguez, X.A., Rubio-Ordoñez, A., 2019. Roofing slate
739 industry in Spain: History, geology, and geoheritage. *Geoheritage* 11(1), 19-34,
740 doi.org/10.1007/s12371-017-0263-y.
- 741 Cárdenes, V., Rubio-Ordoñez, A., Monterroso, C., Calleja, L., 2013. Geology and geochemistry
742 of Iberian roofing slates. *Chem. Erde* 73, 373–382.
- 743 Cárdenes, V., Rubio-Ordoñez, A., Wichert, J., Cnudde, J.P., Cnudde, V., 2014. Petrography of
744 roofing slates. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 138, 435–453.
- 745 Cárdenes, V., López-Sánchez, M.A., Barou, F., Olona, J., Llana-Fúnez, S., 2021. Crystallographic
746 preferred orientation, seismic velocity and anisotropy in roofing slates. *Tectonophysics* 808:
747 228815. DOI: 10.1016/j.tecto.2021.228815.
- 748 Cholach, P.Y., Schmitt, D.R., 2006. Intrinsic elasticity of a textured phyllosilicate aggregate:
749 relation to the seismic anisotropy of shales and schists, *J. Geophys. Res.* 111:B09410,
750 doi:10.1029/2005JB004158.
- 751 Christensen, N.I., Mooney, W.D., 1965. Seismic velocity structure and composition of the
752 continental crust: A global view. *J. Geophys. Res.* 100, 9761-9788, doi:10.1029/95JB00259.
- 753 Clauer, N., Weh, A., 2014. Time constraints for the tectono-thermal evolution of the Cantabrian
754 Zone in NW Spain by illite K-Ar dating. *Tectonophysics* 623, 39-51,
755 doi:10.1016/j.tecto.2014.03.013.
- 756 Cosgrove, J.W., 1976. The formation of crenulation cleavage. *J. Geol. Soc.* 132, 155-178,
757 doi:10.1144/gsjgs.132.2.0155.
- 758 De Boer, R.B., 1977. Pressure solution: theory and experiments. *Tectonophysics* 39, 287-301,
759 doi:10.1016/0040-1951(77)90101-9.
- 760 Díaz, J., Gallart, J., Ruiz, M., Pulgar, J. A., López, C., González-Cortina, J. M., 2006. Probing
761 seismic anisotropy in North Iberia from shear wave splitting, *Phys. Earth Planet. Int.* 158,
762 210–225, doi:10.1016/j.pepi.2005.12.011.
- 763 Dieterich, J.H., 1969. Origin of slaty cleavage in folded rocks. *Am. J. Sci.* 267, 155-165,
764 doi:10.2475/ajs.267.2.155.

- 765 Díez Balda, M.A, Vegas, R., González Lodeiro, F., 1990. Central-Iberian Zone. Structure. In:
766 Dallmeyer RD, Martínez García E, (eds.) Pre-Mesozoic Geology of Iberia, Springer, pp 172-
767 188.
- 768 Díez Balda, M.A., Martínez Catalán, J.R., Ayarza Arribas, P., 1995. Syn-collisional extensional
769 collapse parallel to the orogenic trend in a domain of steep tectonics: the Salamanca
770 Detachment Zone (Central Iberian Zone, Spain). *J. Struct. Geol.* 17, 163-182.
- 771 Durney, D.W., 1972. Solution transfer, an important geological deformation mechanism. *Nature*
772 235, 315-317, doi:10.1038/235315a0.
- 773 Fazio, E., Punturo, R., Cirrincione, R., Kern, H., Pezzino, A., Wenk, H.-R., Goswami, S.,
774 Mamtani, M.A., 2017. Quartz preferred orientation in naturally deformed mylonitic rocks
775 (Montalto Shear Zone - Italy): a comparison of results by different techniques, their
776 advantages and limitations. *Int. J. Earth Sciences* 106, 2259-2278 doi:10.1007/s00531-016-
777 1424-y
- 778 García-Guinea, J., Lombardero, M., Roberts, B., Peto, A., 1998. Mineralogy and microstructure
779 of roofing slate: thermo-optical behaviour and fissility. *Mater. Constr.* 48, 37–48.
- 780 García-Guinea, J., Lombardero, M., Roberts, B., Taboada, J., 1997. Spanish roofing slate
781 deposits. *Trans. Inst. Min. Metall., Sect. B* 106, 205–214.
- 782 Godfrey, N.J., Christensen, N.I., Okaya, D.A., 2000. Anisotropy of schists: Contribution of
783 crustal anisotropy to active source seismic experiments and shear wave splitting
784 observations. *J. Geoph. Res.* 105 (B12), 27991-28007, doi:10.1029/2000JB900286.
- 785 Goldstein, A., Knight, J., Kimball, K., 1998. Deformed graptolites, finite strain and volume loss
786 during cleavage formation in rocks of the taconic slate belt, New York and Vermont, USA. *J.*
787 *Struct. Geol.*, 20, 1769-82.
- 788 Gómez Barreiro, J., Martínez Catalán, J.R., Arenas, R., Castiñeiras, P., Abati, J., Díaz García, F.,
789 Wijbrans, J.R., 2007. Tectonic evolution of the upper allochthon of the Órdenes Complex
790 (northwestern Iberian Massif): structural constraints to a polyorogenic peri-Gondwanan
791 terrane. *Special paper Geol, Soc, America* 423, 315-332

- 792 Gómez Barreiro, J., Catalán, J.R.M., Díez Fernández, R., Arenas, R., Diaz Garcia, F., 2010.
793 Upper crust reworking during gravitational collapse: the Bembibre–Pico Sacro detachment
794 system (NW Iberia). *J. Geol. Soc.* 167, 769-784.
- 795 Gómez-Fernández, F., Castañón, A.M., Ward, C.R., 2012. Analysis of the methodology of the
796 petrographic examination test (European Standard EN 12326-2) and the relation between
797 petrography and modulus of rupture for Spanish roofing slates. *Engineering Geology* 141,
798 114-123.
- 799 González Lodeiro, F., Martínez Catalán, J. R., De Pablo Maciá, J. G., Pérez González, A., 1979.
800 Mapa Geológico de España e. 1:50.000, Hoja No. 48 (08-05) (Meira). Instituto Geológico y
801 Minero de España, Madrid.
- 802 Gray, D.R., 1977. Some parameters which effect the morphology of crenulation cleavage. *J Geol*
803 85, 763-780.
- 804 Gray, D.R., Durney, D. W., 1979. Crenulation cleavage differentiation: implications of solution-
805 deposition processes. *J. Struct. Geol.* 1, 73-80, doi:10.1016/0191-8141(79)90023-3.
- 806 Guggenheim, S., Chang, Y.H., Koster van Groos, A.F., 1987. Muscovite dehydroxylation: High
807 temperature studies. *Am. Mineral.* 72, 537-550.
- 808 Guo, B.B., Wang, H.C., Zhao, W.H., Ji, S.C., Sun, D.S., Li, A.W., Long, C.X., 2014. Analysis of
809 seismic anisotropy of the typical slate from the Gaoligong mountains, Yunnan province, China.
810 *Chin. J. Geophys.* 57, 154–165.
- 811 Gutiérrez-Marco, J.C., Robardet, M., Rábano, I., Sarmiento, G.N., San José Lancha, M.A.,
812 Herranz Araújo, P., Pieren Pidal, A.P., 2002. Ordovician. In: Gibbons, W., Moreno, T. (eds)
813 *The Geology of Spain*. The Geological Society, London, pp. 31–49.
- 814 Gutiérrez-Marco, J.C., Piçarra, J.M., Meireles, C.A., Cózar, P., García-Bellido, D.C., Pereira, Z.,
815 Vaz, N., Pereira, S., Lopes, G., Oliveira, J.T., Quesada, C., Zamora, S., Esteve, J., Colmenar,
816 J., Bernárdez, E., Coronado, I., Lorenzo, S., Sá, A. A., Dias da Silva, Í., González-Clavijo,
817 E., Díez-Montes, A., Gómez-Barreiro, J., 2019. Early Ordovician–Devonian passive margin
818 stage in the Gondwanan units of the Iberian Massif. In: Quesada C., Oliveira T. (eds) *The*
819 *geology of Iberia: A geodynamic approach*, Springer pp 75-98.

- 820 Haerinck, T., Wenk, H.-R., Debacker, T., Sintubin, M., 2015. Preferred mineral orientation in a
821 chloritoid-bearing slate in relation to its magnetic fabric. *J. Struct. Geol.* 71(2), 125-135.
- 822 Herbosch, A., Liégeois, J.P., Gärtner, A., Hofmann, M., Linnemann, U., 2020. The Stavelot-Venn
823 Massif (Ardenne, Belgium), a rift shoulder basin ripped off the West African craton:
824 Cartography, stratigraphy, sedimentology, new U-Pb on zircon ages, geochemistry and Nd
825 isotopes evidence. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 203, 103142.
- 826 Heyliger, P., Ledbetter, H., Kim, S., 2003. Elastic constants of natural quartz. *J. Acoustical Soc.*
827 *America* 114, 644-650, *doi:10.1121/1.1593063*.
- 828 Hill, R., 1952. The elastic behaviour of a crystalline aggregate. *Proc. Phys. Soc. Section A* 65,
829 349-354.
- 830 Ho, N.-C., Peacor, D.R., van der Pluijm, B.A., 1995. Reorientation mechanisms of
831 phyllosilicates in the mudstone-to-slate transition at Lehigh Gap, Pennsylvania. *J. Struct.*
832 *Geol.* 17, 345-356, *doi:10.1016/0191-8141(94)00065-8*.
- 833 Ho, N.-C., van der Pluijm, B.A., Peacor, D.R., 2001. Static recrystallization and preferred
834 orientation of phyllosilicates: Michigamme Formation, northern Michigan, USA. *J. Struct.*
835 *Geol.* 23, 887-893, *doi:10.1016/S0191-8141(00)00162-0*.
- 836 Hornby, B.E., 1998. Experimental laboratory determination of the dynamic elastic properties of
837 wet, drained shales. *J. Geophys. Res.* 103, 29945-29964, *doi:10.1029/97JB02380*.
- 838 Hughes, J.M., Cameron, M., Crowley, K.D., 1989. Structural variations in natural F, OH, and Cl
839 apatites. *Am. Mineral.* 74, 870-876.
- 840 Hutchinson, W.B., Nes, E., 1992. Texture development during grain growth – a useful rule-of-
841 thumb. *Proc. Grain Growth in Polycrystalline Materials I. Materials Science Forum* 94-96,
842 385-390.
- 843 Imon, R., Okudaira, T., Kanagawa, K., 2004. Development of shape and lattice-preferred
844 orientations of amphibole grains during initial cataclastic deformation and subsequent
845 deformation by dissolution-precipitation creep in amphibolites from the Ryoke metamorphic
846 belt, SW Japan. *J. Struct. Geol.* 26, 793-805.

- 847 Ishii, K., 1988. Grain growth and re-orientation of phyllosilicate minerals during the
848 development of slaty cleavage in the South Kitakami Mountains, northeast Japan. *J. Struct.*
849 *Geol.* 10, 145-154, doi:10.1016/0191-8141(88)90112-5.
- 850 Jacques, D., Derez, T., Muchez, P., Sintubin, M., 2014. Syn- to late-orogenic quartz veins
851 marking a retrograde deformation path in a slate belt: Examples from the High-Ardenne slate
852 belt (Belgium). *J. Struct. Geol.* 58, 43-58.
- 853 Jeffery, G.B., 1923. The motion of ellipsoidal particles immersed in a viscous fluid. *Proc. R. Soc.*
854 *London* 102, 161-179.
- 855 Ji, S.C., Shao, T.B., Michibayashi, K., Oya, S., Satsukawa, T., Wang, Q., Zhao, W.H., Salisbury,
856 M.H., 2015. Magnitude and symmetry of seismic anisotropy in mica- and amphibole-bearing
857 metamorphic rocks and implications for tectonic interpretation of seismic data from the
858 southeast Tibetan Plateau. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 120, 6404–6430.
- 859 Julivert, M., Fontbote, J.M., Ribeiro, A., Nabais Condé, L.E., 1972. Mapa Tectónico de la
860 Península Ibérica y Baleares E. 1:1.000.000. Inst. Geol. Min. Esp. Madrid.
- 861 Kamb, W.B., 1959. Theory of preferred crystal orientation developed by crystallization under
862 stress. *J. Geology* 67, 153-170.
- 863 Kanagawa, K., 1991. Change in dominant mechanisms for phyllosilicate preferred orientation
864 during cleavage development in the Kitakami slates of NE Japan. *J. Struct. Geol.* 13 (8), 927-
865 943.
- 866 Kanitpanyacharoen, W., Kets, F.B., Wenk, H.-R., Wirth, R., 2012. Preferred orientation,
867 microstructures and porosity analyses of Posidonia shales. *Clays and Clay Minerals* 60, 315-
868 329, doi:10.1346/CCMN.2012.0600308.
- 869 Karasawa, Y. and Kano, K.-i., 1992. Formation and deformation process of the slate belt in the
870 Setogawa Group (the Shimanto Belt) of the eastern Akaishi Mountains, easternmost
871 southwest Japan. *J. Geol. Soc. Japan*, 98, 761-777.
- 872 Kern, H., Popp, T., Gorbatshevich, F., Zharikov, A., Lobanov, K.V., Smirnov, Y.P., 2001.
873 Pressure and temperature dependence of VP and VS in rocks from the superdeep well and
874 from surface analogues at Kola and the nature of velocity anisotropy. *Tectonophysics* 338,
875 113-134.

- 876 Kern, H., Mengel, K., Strauss, K.W., Ivankina, T.I., Nikitin, A.N., Kukkonen, I.T., 2009. Elastic
877 wave velocities, chemistry and modal mineralogy of crustal rocks sampled by the
878 Outokumpu scientific drill hole. *Phys. Earth Planet. Int.* 175, 151-166
- 879 Knipe, R.J., 1979. Chemical changes during slaty cleavage development. *Bull. Mineral.* 102,
880 206-209.
- 881 Knipe, R.J., 1981. The interaction of deformation and metamorphism in slates. *Tectonophysics*
882 78, 249-272, doi:10.1016/0040-1951(81)90016-0.
- 883 Knipe, R.J., White, S.H., 1977. Microstructural variation of an axial plane cleavage around a
884 fold. A H.V.E.M. study. *Tectonophysics* 39, 355-381.
- 885 Kröner, E., 1958. Berechnung der elastischen Konstanten des Vielkristalls aus den Konstanten
886 des Einkristalls. *Zeitschrift Physik* 151, 504-518.
- 887 Large, D.J., Christy, A.G., Fallick, A.E., 1994. Poorly crystalline carbonaceous matter in high
888 grade metasediments: implications for graphitisation and metamorphic fluid composition.
889 *Contrib. Mineral. Petrog.* 116, 108-116.
- 890 Lee, J.H., Peacor, D.R., Lewis, D.D., Wintsch, R.P., 1986. Evidence for syntectonic
891 crystallization for the mudstone to slate transition at Lehigh Gap, Pennsylvania, USA. *J.*
892 *Struct. Geol.* 8, 767-780, doi:10.1016/0191-8141(86)90024-6.
- 893 Lokajicek, T., Vasin, R., Svitek, T., Petruzalek, M., Kotrly, M., Turkova, I., Onysko, R., Wenk,
894 H.-R., 2020. Intrinsic elastic anisotropy of Westerly granite observed by ultrasound
895 measurements, microstructural investigations, and neutron diffraction. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid*
896 *Earth* 126, e2020JB020878, [doi.org/10.1029/2020JB020878].
- 897 Lutterotti, L., Matthies, S., Wenk, H.-R., Schultz, A.J., Richardson, J.W., 1997. Combined
898 texture and structure analysis of deformed limestone from time-of-flight neutron diffraction
899 spectra. *J. Appl. Phys.* 81, 594-600, doi:10.1063/1.364220.
- 900 Lutterotti, L., Chateigner, D., Ferrari, S., Ricote, J., 2004. Texture, residual stress and structural
901 analysis of thin films using a combined X-ray analysis. *Thin Solid Films* 450, 34-41,
902 doi:10.1016/j.tsf.2003.10.150.

- 903 Lutterotti, L., Vasin, R., Wenk, H.-R., 2014. Rietveld texture analysis from synchrotron
904 diffraction images. I. Calibration and basic analysis. *Powder Diffraction* 29, 76-84,
905 doi:10.1017/S0885715613001346.
- 906 Makarynska, D., Gurevich, B., Ciz, R., Arns, C.H., Knackstedt, M.A., 2008. Finite element
907 modelling of the effective elastic properties of partially saturated rocks. *Computers*
908 *Geosciences* 34, 647-657.
- 909 March, A., 1932. Mathematische Theorie der Regelung nach der Korngestalt bei affiner
910 Deformation. *Zeitschrift für Kristallographie* 81, 285-297.
- 911 Martínez Catalán, J.R., Hacar Rodríguez, M.P., Villar Alonso, P., Pérez-Estaún, A., González
912 Lodeiro, F., 1992. Lower Paleozoic extensional tectonics in the limit between the West
913 Asturian-Leonese and Central Iberian Zones of the Variscan fold-belt in NW Spain. *Geol.*
914 *Rundschau* 81, 545-560.
- 915 Martínez Catalán, J.R., Fernández-Suárez, J., Jenner, G.A., Belousova, E., Díez Montes, A.,
916 2004. Provenance constraints from detrital zircon U–Pb ages in the NW Iberian Massif:
917 implications for Palaeozoic plate configuration and Variscan evolution. *J. Geol. Soc.* 161,
918 463-476.
- 919 Martínez Catalán, J.R., Rubio Pascual, F.J., Montes, A.D., Fernández, R.D., Gomez Barreiro, J.,
920 Dias Da Silva, Í., Clavijo, E.G., Ayarza, P., Alcock, J.E., 2014. The late Variscan HT/LP
921 metamorphic event in NW and Central Iberia: relationships to crustal thickening, extension,
922 orocline development and crustal evolution. In Schulmann K, Martínez Catalán JR, Lardeaux
923 JM, Janousek V, Oggiano G, (eds) *The Variscan Orogeny: Extent, Timescale and the*
924 *Formation of the European Crust.* Geol. Soc. London Spec. Pub. 405, London, pp 225-247
- 925 Matthies, S., 2010. On the combination of self-consistent and geometric mean elements for the
926 calculation of the elastic properties of textured multi-phase samples, *Solid State Phenom.*
927 160, 87–93.
- 928 Matthies, S., 2012. GEO-MIX-SELF calculations of the elastic properties of a textured graphite
929 sample at different hydrostatic pressures. *J. Appl. Cryst.* 45, 1–16.

- 930 Matthies, S., Vinel, G.W., 1982. On the reproduction of the orientation distribution function of
931 texturized samples from reduced pole figures using the conception of a conditional ghost
932 correction. *Phys. Stat. Solidi (b)* 112, K111-114.
- 933 Matthies, S., Humbert, M., 1995. On the principle of a geometric mean of even-rank symmetric
934 tensors for textured polycrystals. *J. Appl. Cryst.* 28, 254-266.
- 935 Matthies, S., Priesmeyer, H.G., Daymond, M.R., 2001. On the diffractive determination of
936 single-crystal elastic constants using polycrystalline samples. *J. Appl. Cryst.* 34, 585-601.
- 937 Matthies, S., Wenk, H.-R., 2009. Transformations for monoclinic crystal symmetry in texture
938 analysis. *J. Appl. Cryst.* 42, 564-571, doi:10.1107/S0021889809018172.
- 939 Means, W.D., 1981. The concept of steady-state foliation. *Tectonophysics* 78(1-4), 179-199,
940 doi:10.1016/0040-1951(81)90013-5.
- 941 Menegon, L., Pennacchioni, G., Heilbronner, R., Pittarello, L., 2008. Evolution of quartz
942 microstructure and c-axis crystallographic preferred orientation within ductilely deformed
943 granitoids (Arolla Unit, Western Alps). *J. Struct. Geol.* 30(11), 1332-1347,
944 doi:10.1016/j.jsg.2008.07.007.
- 945 Minor, A., Rybacki, E., Sintubin, M., Vogel, S., Wenk, H.-R., 2018. Tracking mechanical
946 Dauphiné twin evolution with applied stress in axial compression experiments on a low-
947 grade metamorphic rock. *J. Struct. Geol.* 112, 81-94, doi:10.1016/j.jsg.2018.04.002.
- 948 Mookherjee, M., Mainprice, D., 2014. Unusually large shear wave anisotropy for chlorite in
949 subduction zone settings. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 41, 1506-1513.
- 950 Morris, A.P., 1981. Competing deformation mechanisms and slaty cleavage in deformed,
951 quartzose meta-sediments. *J. Geol. Soc. London* 138(4), 455-462
952 doi:10.1144/gsjgs.138.4.0455.
- 953 Morris, P.R., 1970. Elastic constants of polycrystals. *Int. J. Engin. Sci.* 8, 49-61.
- 954 Nye, J.F., 1985 *The Physical Properties of Crystals: Their Representation by Tensors and*
955 *Matrices.* Oxford University Press, Oxford. 330 pp.
- 956 Oertel, G., 1983. The relationship of strain and preferred orientation of phyllosilicate grains in
957 rocks-a review. *Tectonophysics* 100, 413-447, doi:10.1016/0040-1951(83)90197-X.

- 958 Oertel, G., Curtis, C.D., 1972. Clay ironstone concretion preserving fabrics due to progressive
959 compaction. *Geol. Soc. America Bull.* 83, 2597-2606, doi:10.1130/0016-
960 7606(1972)83[2597:CCPFDT]2.0.CO;2.
- 961 Oertel, G., Curtis, C.D., Phakey, P.P., 1973. A transmission electron microscope and x-ray
962 diffraction study of muscovite and chlorite. *Mineral. Mag.* 39, 176-188,
963 doi:10.1180/minmag.1973.039.302.05.
- 964 Oertel, G., Phakey, P.P., 1972. The texture of a slate from Nantlle, Caernarvon, North Wales.
965 *Texture* 1, 1-8, doi:10.1155/TSM.1.1.
- 966 Pabst, A., 1931. „Pressure-Shadows“ and the measurement of the orientation of minerals in
967 rocks. *Am. Mineral.* 16, 55-70
- 968 Palomeras, I., Ayarza, P., Andrés, J., Álvarez-Valero, A.M., Gómez-Barreiro, J., Díaz J.,
969 Alcalde, J., Carbonell, R., 2021. Mapping and Interpreting the Uppermost Mantle
970 Reflectivity beneath Central and South-West Iberia. *J. Geophys. Res.* 126: e2020JB019987.
- 971 Passchier, C.W., Trouw, R.A.J., 2005. *Microtectonics* (2nd Edn). Springer ISBN 978-3-540-
972 29359-0.
- 973 Pehl, J., Wenk, H.-R., 2005. Evidence for regional Dauphiné twinning in quartz from the Santa
974 Rosa mylonite zone in Southern California. A neutron diffraction study. *J. Struct. Geol.* 27,
975 1741-1749, doi:10.1107/S0021889805006059.
- 976 Pérez-Estaún, A., Martínez-Catalán, J.R., Bastida, F., 1991. Crustal thickening and deformation
977 sequence in the footwall to the suture of the Variscan belt of northwest Spain.
978 *Tectonophysics* 191, 243–253.
- 979 Plessmann, W. Von, 1964. Gesteinslösung, ein Hauptfaktor beim Schieferungsprozess. *Geol.*
980 *Mitt. Aachen* 4, 69-82.
- 981 Plessmann, W. Von, 1966. Lösung, Verformung, Transport und Gefüge. *Z. Dtsch. Geol. Ges.*
982 115, 650-663.
- 983 Popa, N.C., 1998. The (hkl) dependence of diffraction-line broadening caused by strain and size
984 for all Laue groups in Rietveld refinement. *J. Appl. Cryst.* 31, 176-180.

- 985 Reuss, A., 1929. Berechnung der Fließgrenze von Mischkristallen auf Grund der
986 Plastizitätsbedingung für Einkristalle. *Z. Angewandte Mathematik Mechanik* 9, 49-58.
- 987 Rietveld, H.M., 1969. A profile refinement method for nuclear and magnetic structures. *J. Appl.*
988 *Cryst.* 2, 65-71. doi:10.1107/S0021889869006558.
- 989 Ruiz, M., Diaz, J., Pedreira, D., Gallart, J., Pulgar, J.A., 2017. Crustal structure of the North
990 Iberian continental margin from seismic refraction/wide-angle reflection profiles.
991 *Tectonophysics* 717, 65-82.
- 992 Rutter, E.H., 1976. The kinetics of rock deformation by pressure solution. *Phil Trans Roy Soc*
993 *London A* 283, 203-219, doi:10.1098/rsta.1976.0079.
- 994 Shimizu, I., 1992. Nonhydrostatic and nonequilibrium thermodynamics of deformable materials.
995 *J. Geophys. Res.* 97 (B4), 4587-4597, doi:10.1029/91JB02859.
- 996 Shimizu, I., 2008. Theories and applicability of grain size piezometers: The role of dynamic
997 recrystallization mechanisms. *J. Struct. Geol.* 30:899-917.
- 998 Siddans, A.W.B., 1972. Slaty cleavage: a review of research since 1815. *Earth Science Reviews*
999 8(2), 205-212.
- 1000 Sintubin, M., 1994. Phyllosilicate preferred orientation in relation to strain path determination in
1001 the lower Paleozoic Stavelot-Venn Massif (Ardennes, Belgium). *Tectonophysics* 237, 215-
1002 231, doi:10.1016/0040-1951(94)90256-9.
- 1003 Sorby, H.C., 1853. On the origin of slaty cleavage. *New Philos. J. (Edinburgh)* 55, 137-148.
- 1004 Sorby, H.C., 1856. On the theory of the origin of slaty cleavage. *Phil. Mag.* 12, 127-129.
- 1005 Srisutthiyakorn, N., Hunter, S., Sarker, R., Hofmann, R., Espejo, I., 2018. Predicting elastic
1006 properties and permeability of rocks from 2D thin sections. *The Leading Edge* 37, 402-480.
- 1007 Suárez-Ruiz, I., Flores, D., Graciano Mendonça Filho, J., Hackley, P.C., 2012. Review and
1008 update of the applications of organic petrology: Part 1, geological applications. *Int. J. Coal*
1009 *Geol.* 99, 54-112.
- 1010 Suchy, V., Sykorova, I., Melka, K., Filip, J., Machovic, V., 2007. Illite ‘crystallinity’, maturation
1011 of organic matter and microstructural development associated with lowest-grade

- 1012 metamorphism of Neoproterozoic sediments in the Tepla-Barrandian unit, Czech Republic.
1013 Clay Minerals 42 (4), 503-526.
- 1014 Toy, V.G., Prior, D.J., Norris, R.J., 2008. Quartz fabrics in the Alpine Fault mylonites: Influence
1015 of pre-existing preferred orientations on fabric development during progressive uplift. J.
1016 Struct. Geol. 30(5), 602-621, doi:10.1016/j.jsg.2008.01.001.
- 1017 Turnbull, I.M., Mortimer, N., Craw, D., 2001. Textural zones in the Haast Schist—a reappraisal,
1018 New Zealand J. Geol. Geophys. 44, 1, 171-183, DOI: 10.1080/00288306.2001.9514933
- 1019 Ulian, G., Moro, D., Valdre, G., 2018. First principle investigation of the mechanical properties
1020 of natural layered nanocomposite: Clinocllore as a model system for heterodesmic
1021 structures. Composite Structures 202, 551-558.
- 1022 Valcke, S.L.A., Casey, M., Lloyd, G.E., Kendall, J.-M., Fisher, Q.J., 2006. Lattice preferred
1023 orientation and seismic anisotropy in sedimentary rocks. Geophysical J. Intern. 166, 652-666,
1024 doi:10.1111/j.1365-246X.2006.02987.x.
- 1025 Van Norden, M., Sintubin, M., Darboux, J.-R., 2007. Incipient strain partitioning in a slate belt:
1026 Evidence from the early Variscan Monts d'Arrée slate belt (Brittany, France). J. Struct. Geol.
1027 29(5). 837-849.
- 1028 Vasin, R., Wenk, H.-R., Kanitpanyacharoen, W., Matthies, S., Wirth, R., 2013. Anisotropy of
1029 Kimmeridge shale. J. Geophys. Res. 118, 1-26, doi:10.1002/jgrb.50259.
- 1030 Vasin, R., Kern, H., Lokajicek, T., Svitek, T., Lehmann, E., Mannes, D.C., Chaouche, M., Wenk,
1031 H.-R., 2017. Elastic anisotropy of Tambo gneiss from Promontogno, Switzerland: a
1032 comparison of crystal orientation and microstructure-based modeling and experimental
1033 measurements. Geophys. J. Int. 209, 1-20, doi:10.1093/gji/ggw487.
- 1034 Vaughan, M.T., Guggenheim, S., 1986. Elasticity of muscovite and its relationship to crystal
1035 structure. J. Geophys. Res. 91:4657-4664, DOI:10.1029/JB091iB05P04657.
- 1036 Vernik, L., Liu, X., 1997. Velocity anisotropy in shales: A petrophysical study. Geophysics 62,
1037 521-532, doi:10.1190/1.1444162.
- 1038 Voigt, W., 1887. Theoretische Studien über die Elasticitätsverhältnisse der Krystalle.
1039 Dieterichsche Verlags-Buchhandlung, Göttingen. 100 pp.

- 1040 Voltolini, M., Wenk, H.-R., Mondol, N.H., Bjørlykke, K., Jahren, J., 2009. Anisotropy of
1041 experimentally compressed kaolinite-illite-quartz mixtures. *Geophysics* 74, D13-D23, doi:
1042 10.1190/1.3002557.
- 1043 Wagner, W., 2007. The basics of test methods of slates for roofing and cladding. *Grundlagen für*
1044 *die Prüfung von Dach- und Wandschiefern. Z. Dtsch. Ges. Geowiss.* 158, 785–805.
- 1045 Ward, C.R., Gómez-Fernández, F., 2003. Quantitative mineralogical analysis of Spanish roofing
1046 slates using the Rietveld method and X-ray powder diffraction data. *Europ. J. Mineral.* 15,
1047 1051-1062.
- 1048 Weber, K., 1981. Kinematic and metamorphic aspects of cleavage formation in very low-grade
1049 metamorphic slates. *Tectonophysics* 78, 291-306, doi:10.1016/0040-1951(81)90018-4.
- 1050 Wenk, H.-R., Matthies S., Donovan J., Chateigner D., 1998. BEARTEX: a Windows-based
1051 program system for quantitative texture analysis. *J. Appl. Cryst.* 31, 262-269,
1052 doi:10.1107/S002188989700811X.
- 1053 Wenk, H.-R., Lutterotti, L., Vogel, S., 2003. Texture analysis with the new HIPPO TOF
1054 diffractometer. *Nucl. Instr. Methods A* 515, 575-588 doi:10.1016/j.nima.2003.05.001
- 1055 Wenk, H.-R., Voltolini, M., Kern, H., Popp, H., Mazurek, M., 2008. Anisotropy of Mont Terri
1056 Opalinus Clay. *The Leading Edge* 27, 742-748
- 1057 Wenk, H.-R., Kanitpanyacharoen, W., Voltolini, M., 2010. Preferred orientation of
1058 phyllosilicates: comparison of fault gouge, shale and schist. *J. Struct. Geol.* 32, 478-489,
1059 doi:10.1016/j.jsg.2010.02.003.
- 1060 Wenk, H.-R., Vasin, R.N., Kern, H., Matthies, S., Vogel, S.C., Ivankina, T.I., 2012. Revisiting
1061 elastic anisotropy of biotite gneiss from the Outokumpu scientific drill hole based on new
1062 texture measurements and texture-based velocity calculations. *Tectonophysics* 570-571, 123-
1063 134 [doi:10.1016/j.tecto.2012.06.023]
- 1064 Wenk, H.-R., Lutterotti, L., Kaercher, P., Kanitpanyacharoen, W., Miyagi, L., Vasin, R., 2014.
1065 Rietveld texture analysis from synchrotron diffraction images: II. Complex multiphase
1066 materials and diamond anvil cell experiments. *Powder Diffraction* 29, 220-232,
1067 doi:10.1017/S0885715614000360.

- 1068 Wenk, H.-R., Kanitpanyacharoen, W., Ren, Y., 2019. Slate – a new record for crystal preferred
1069 orientation. *J. Struct. Geol.* 125 (50 year special issue), 319-324,
1070 doi:10.1016/j.jsg.2017.12.009.
- 1071 Wenk, H.-R., Yu, R., Cardenes, V., Lopez-Sanchez, M.A., Sintubin, M., 2020. Review: Fabric
1072 and anisotropy of slates: From classical studies to new results. *J. Struct. Geol.* 138, 104066
1073 [doi:10.1016/j.jsg.2020.104066]
- 1074 Weyl, P.K., 1959. Pressure solution and force of crystallisation-A phenomenological theory. *J.*
1075 *Geophys. Res.* 64(11), 2001-2025, doi:10.1029/JZ064i011p02001.
- 1076 White, S.H., Knipe, R.J., 1978. Microstructure and cleavage development in selected slates.
1077 *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.* 66(2), 165-174, doi:10.1007/BF00372155.
- 1078 Williams, P.F., 1977. Relationship between axial plane foliation and strain. *Tectonophysics* 30,
1079 181-196.
- 1080 Winter, J.K., Ghose, S., Okamura, F.P., 1977. A high-temperature study of the thermal
1081 expansion and the anisotropy of the sodium atom in low albite. *Am. Mineral.* 62, 921-931.
- 1082 Wood, D. S., 1974. Current views of the development of slaty cleavage. *Ann. Rev. Earth. Sci.* 2,
1083 1-35.
- 1084 Wood, D.S., Oertel, G., Singh, J., Bennett, H.F., 1976. A discussion of natural strain and
1085 geological structure - Strain and anisotropy in rocks. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. London* 283, 27-42,
1086 doi:10.1098/rsta.1976.0067.
- 1087 Wood, D.S., Oertel, G., 1980. Deformation in the Cambrian slate belt of Wales. *J. Geol.* 88(3) ,
1088 309-26.
- 1089 Wright, T.O., Platt, L.B., 1982. Pressure dissolution and cleavage in the Martinsburg Shale. *Am.*
1090 *J. Sci.* 282(2) , 122-135, doi:10.2475/ajs.282.2.122.
- 1091 Zanazzi, P.F., Comodi, P., Nazzareni, S., Andreozzi, G.B., 2009. Thermal behaviour of chlorite:
1092 an in situ single-crystal and powder diffraction study. *Europ. J. Mineral.* 21, 581-589.
- 1093 Zhong, X., Frehner, M., Kunze, K., Zappone, A., 2014 A novel EBSD-based finite-element wave
1094 propagation model for investigating seismic anisotropy: Application to Finero Peridotite,
1095 Ivrea-Verbano Zone, Northern Italy. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 41, 7105-7114.

1097 Figures

1098 Fig. 1. (a) Geological map of the Variscan orogen in the Iberian Peninsula. Samples were collected
1099 in three different domains: Sa1 in Schist-Greywacke Complex (SGC), Lugo1 in Mondoñedo
1100 Nappe of WALZ domain and Bv, Heb, Fo and Piv in Ollo de Sapo domain. The location of
1101 the studied areas (red squares) is indicated. The zones of the Variscan Iberian Massif and major
1102 faults and strike-slip shear zones are highlighted (after Martínez Catalán et al., 2014). (b)
1103 Geological map of the Truchas syncline and surrounding areas. (c) Geological section (I-II).
1104 Dashed lines represent axial planes of recumbent folds (C1). C2 Thrusts overprinted C1 folds
1105 and both appear refolded by later C3 upright folds. Red squares: locations of the samples. c)
1106 Stratigraphic legend and ages (after Gutiérrez Marcos et al., 2019).

1107 Fig. 2. Hand specimens of slates. (a) Phyllite Sa1 with crenulation lineation, (b) black slate Os
1108 Follos Fo3 with no quartz, (c) slate Fo8 with diagonal bedding (S0) and slaty cleavage (S1)
1109 (vertical). Coin with 2cm diameter (a) is for scale for all.

1110 Fig. 3. Roofing slates: (a) Lugo1, green. (b) Piv1, Luarca Fm. black slate. Black slates from Luarca
1111 formation are very homogeneous. (c) Os Follos Fo9 black-slate (1st quality tiles). In all cases,
1112 tile width is 21 cm, thickness varies from 9 mm (Lugo1), 5mm (Piv1) to 2.5 mm (Fo9). Scale
1113 is 30 cm.

1114 Fig. 4. Detail of the Os Follos quarry, from where most of our samples come from (Fo-samples).
1115 Slate extraction is focused on the lower part of the quarry (black slates level) just below the Os
1116 Follos quartzite (Barros Lorenzo 1989) with minor folds (highlighted in yellow) and S0/S1
1117 relationship (dashed red line).

1118 Fig. 5 (a-l). SEM-BE images of slate samples cut perpendicular to cleavage (XY) and lineation
1119 (X) . Phases identified using SEM-EDS and labelled as chlorite (C), muscovite (M), quartz
1120 (Q), albite (Ab), apatite (Ap) and monazite (Mo). All scale bars are 10 μm unless otherwise
1121 labeled. Images were taken in high vacuum mode at a working distance of 15 mm and
1122 accelerating voltage of 20 kV

1123 Fig. 6 (a-f). SEM-BE images of details in some samples as discussed in the text. Phases
1124 identified using SEM-EDS are chlorite (C), muscovite (M), quartz (Q), albite (Ab), apatite
1125 (Ap), biotite (Bi), ilmenite (Il) and monazite (Mo). (g-i) Some details about crenulation

1126 cleavage in phyllite Sa1. (g) Different domains outlined on the SEM image. (h) Schematic
1127 outlining microlithon and cleavage domain. Cleavage domain, predominantly defined by
1128 muscovite, correspond to C3 compressional foliation (S3, red dashed lines). Within
1129 microlithons transposed relics of the S1 foliation are preserved (blue solid lines). (i) 3D
1130 image of crenulation and lineation.

1131 Fig. 7. Schematic of X-ray diffraction experiment with X-ray beam, sample mounted on a
1132 goniometer head and rotated (ϕ) and detector with diffraction image. Upper left is the pole-
1133 figure coverage with 11 images taken at different angles ϕ . Note that there is excellent
1134 coverage in the center (X) for the main orientation maximum (001 of phyllosilicates).

1135 Fig. 8. Selected diffraction images for (a) Fo3 (without quartz) and (b) Fo4 (with quartz).
1136 Intensity variations along Debye rings are indicative of preferred orientation. In (b) for quartz
1137 100 and 101 there are no intensity variations and thus no CPO. Cleavage plane is vertical.

1138 Fig. 9. “Unrolled” diffraction image of Fo3 (Fig. 8a) in MAUD, plotting azimuthal intensities as
1139 function of $2-\Theta$. This corresponds to a stack of 72 integrated diffraction patterns. Some
1140 diffraction peaks are indexed. Bottom are experimental data and above it the Rietveld fit.

1141 Fig. 10. Pole-figures of muscovite. Equal area projection on cleavage plane. Contours in
1142 multiples of random distribution, logarithmic scale. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are
1143 indicated.

1144 Fig. 11. Pole-figures of chlorite. Equal area projection on cleavage plane. Contours in multiples
1145 of random distribution, logarithmic scale. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are indicated.

1146 Fig. 12. Pole-figures of quartz. Equal area projection on cleavage plane. Contours in multiples of
1147 random distribution, linear scale. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are indicated.

1148 Fig. 13. (001) Pole-figures of apatite in Fo3 and biotite in Sa1. Equal area projection on cleavage
1149 plane. Contours in multiples of random distribution, linear scale.

1150 Fig. 14. SEM-BE image of microstructure in Fo9 with chlorite (C), muscovite (M) and quartz
1151 (Q). Ellipses approximate grain shapes and are used in GeoMixSelf to calculate aggregate
1152 elastic properties.

1153 Fig. 15. P-wave velocity distributions of muscovite, chlorite (projected on cleavage plane (001))
1154 and quartz (with c-axis in center) single crystals. Linear scale. Equal area projection.
1155 Minimum and maximum velocity values and anisotropy coefficient A_n are given.

1156 Fig. 16. P and dS velocities, equal area projection on the cleavage plane, linear scale. The first 11
1157 samples are Spanish slates. The last one is Kimmeridge shale from the North Sea for
1158 comparison and with different intensity scale. Anisotropy coefficient A_n values (%) are
1159 given. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are indicated.

1160 Fig. 17. Comparison of muscovite and chlorite texture, represented by maximum values of 001
1161 plane (m.r.d) and tectosilicates (quartz+ Albite) vol%, calculated from data in Table 2.
1162 Horizontal grey arrow (1) represents the typical compositional range for Spanish roofing
1163 slates, and vertical grey line represents typical tectosilicate content in green phyllites
1164 equivalent to Lugo1 (Cardenes et al. 2014).

1165 **Supplementary Figures**

1166 Suppl. Fig. 1. Geological map of the Schist-Greywacke Complex (SGC) in the Salvatierra area.
1167 The location of sample Sa-1 is indicated. NW-SE upright C3 Variscan folds (axial traces)
1168 dominate the structure in this sector (after Díez Balda et al. 1995). c: conglomerate levels,
1169 white dashed lines.

1170 Suppl. Fig. 2. Geological map (a) and cross section (b) of the sample Lugo-1 in the Mondoñedo
1171 Nappe Domain. Recumbent C1 folds appear refolded by open upright late Variscan folds (C3).
1172 (Modified after González Lodeiro et al. 1979). Thin-dashed lines in (b) represent S1 foliation
1173 pattern.

1174 Suppl. Fig. 3: Overview of the Truchas syncline roofing slate quarries in the area of study. Note
1175 only the best quality slate is exploited. C: Santa María del Casaio; Fo: Os Folloos quarry; R:
1176 Riodalas; SPT: San Pedro de Trones; PDF: Puente de Domingo Flórez. Source: Google Earth
1177 Pro 7.3.3.7786. (7/12/2019). Santa María del Casaio region; NW Spain. 42°19'39''N
1178 6°48'15''W, Eye alt 17.26km. Google 2021. <<http://www.google.com/earth/index.html>>
1179 (Accessed August 8, 2021).

1180

1181 Table 1. Samples and geological setting

Sample	Lithology	Unit	Age	Variscan Domain	Metamorphic grade	References
Bv5b Heb1 Fo2 Fo3 Fo4 Fo7 Fo8a Fo8b Fo9	black slate	Rozadáis	Upper Ordovician	Ollo de Sapo (Truchas syncline)	Greenschist facies (Chlorite zone) 300-400°C	Cárdenes et al. (2014) Barros Lorenzo (1989) García Guinéa et al. (1997)
Piv1	black slate	Luarca	Middle Ordovician			
Lugo1	green slate	Cándana Slates	Lower Cambrian	Mondoñedo Nappe	Greenschist facies <450°C	González Lodeiro et al. (1979) Cárdenes et al. (2014)
Sa1	phyllite	Monterrubio	Upper Proterozoic	Schist-Greywacke Complex	(Biotite zone)	Díez Balda et al. (1995)

1182

1183

1184 Table 2. Volume fraction of each mineral (in %), and accessories (Ab albite, Ap apatite, Bi
 1185 biotite, Ilm ilmenite, Mo monazite, Py pyrite, Ru rutile. Standard deviations of volume fractions
 1186 in parentheses (last digit).

	Quartz	Muscovite	Chlorite	Albite	Accessories
Bv5b	24.8(2)	44.5(3)	24.1(2)	6.5(4)	Ap, Ru
Heb1	26.2(1)	36.7(1)	29.9(1)	7.2(1)	Ap, Py, Ru
Fo2	25.6(1)	38.4(1)	25.6(1)	10.5(1)	Ap, Py, Ru
Fo3	0.1(5)	63.5(6)	36.3(3)		Ab, Ap, Mo, Py, Ru
Fo4	22.1(1)	41.3(2)	27.4(1)	9.2(1)	Py, Ru
Fo7	34.1(1)	45.0(1)	16.4(1)	8.6(1)	Py, Ru
Fo8a	28.3(1)	35.3(1)	26.3(1)	10.1(1)	Mo, Ru
Fo8b	28.3(1)	35.3(1)	26.3(1)	10.1(1)	Ap, Ru
Fo9	26.7(1)	38.9(2)	27.3(1)	7.1(1)	Ap, Mo, Py,
Piv1	31.7(1)	42.3(1)	26.0(1)		Ap, Ru
Lugo1	42.9(1)	40.2(1)	16.8(1)		Ilm
Sa1	31.5(2)	39.4(2)	19.7(1)	9.4(5)	Ap, Bi, Ru

1187

1188

1189 Table 3. Pole densities of crystals in different samples: 001 pole-figure maxima and minima,
 1190 ODF maximum (in multiples of random distribution, mrd) and halfwidth of 001 texture
 1191 maximum in XZ (a) and YZ (b) planes at 1 mrd (boundary between blue and green, in degrees).

	Muscovite				Chlorite				Quartz	
	Min 001	Max 001	ODF max	(001) a-b	Min 001	Max 001	ODF max	(001) a-b	Min 001	Max 001
Bv5b	0.1	56.4	94	21-40	0.1	57.0	354	22-50	0.61	1.51
Heb1	0.0	61.8	184	22-51	0.0	44.4	173	22-45	0.35	1.80
Fo2	0.1	25.2	71	24-52	0.1	21.6	79	23->90	0.41	1.68
Fo3	0.0	69.4	205	20-33	0.1	99.3	503	19-35	-	-
Fo4	0.0	83.5	213	22-36	0.0	83.7	531	21-41	0.43	1.35
Fo7	0.1	38.0	83	24-43	0.0	36.6	660	22-38	0.38	1.70
Fo8a	0.0	29.3	70	22-55	0.0	37.4	143	22-65	0.51	1.43
Fo8b	0.0	36.6	106	22-50	0.0	51.0	132	21-54	0.38	1.54
Fo9	0.0	43.1	138	23-51	0.0	65.1	140	23-50	0.62	1.36
Piv1	0.0	46.7	114	24-33	0.0	57.4	461	22-42	0.52	1.32
Lugo1	0.0	119.8	310	17-32	0.0	125.1	951	16-29	0.15	1.70
Sa1	0.0	41.6	139	18->90	0.1	13.5	88	21->90	0.31	2.23

1192

1193 Table 4. Elastic properties of slates expressed as 21 stiffness coefficients (C_{ij} in GPa); Wave
 1194 velocity maxima and minima (P and dS velocities are in km/s); P-wave anisotropy coefficient
 1195 $An(\%)$; and density (g/cm^3). X is lineation, Z is normal to cleavage.

1196

	Bv5b	Heb1	Fo2	Fo3	Fo4	Fo7	Fo8a	Fo9	Piv1	Lugo1	Sa1
density	2.706	2.684	2.693	2.730	2.696	2.716	2.686	2.692	2.700	2.714	2.701
C_{11}	141.20	142.09	135.02	171.54	144.95	134.58	135.80	139.01	142.72	139.79	131.68
C_{22}	130.40	131.15	119.86	159.95	134.97	124.01	119.67	124.50	136.9	134.28	112.75
C_{33}	83.54	86.72	89.06	77.49	83.76	82.43	90.35	88.29	82.17	78.55	89.26
C_{44}	30.16	30.84	33.23	24.06	29.30	30.66	33.23	31.82	29.31	29.30	34.04
C_{55}	29.84	30.94	33.90	23.94	29.28	30.90	33.70	32.12	29.23	28.74	35.38
C_{66}	51.89	52.29	47.93	59.93	53.65	50.39	48.31	49.74	54.05	54.96	45.82
C_{12}	30.72	30.74	28.76	44.58	31.38	27.64	28.25	29.88	30.99	26.70	26.38
C_{13}	23.23	23.35	24.67	28.77	22.76	21.75	23.31	23.88	22.97	18.72	23.82
C_{14}	0.07	0.11	0.12	0.08	-0.03	-0.25	-0.05	-0.01	0.04	0.75	0.57
C_{15}	-1.42	2.21	-1.07	7.08	0.88	-2.73	1.74	0.38	-5.82	-0.69	-1.20
C_{16}	0.20	-0.29	-0.39	-0.57	-0.27	-0.31	-0.37	-0.01	-0.03	-0.06	-0.09
C_{23}	25.22	25.08	26.64	29.87	24.32	23.26	25.82	26.03	23.99	20.23	25.82
C_{24}	0.49	0.78	0.95	0.71	-0.06	-2.21	-0.04	0.03	0.02	5.95	2.58
C_{25}	-0.17	0.25	-0.13	1.09	0.11	-0.24	0.10	0.01	-0.71	-0.08	0.08
C_{26}	0.09	-0.11	0.15	-0.49	-0.24	-0.25	-0.16	0.02	-0.03	0.17	0.28
C_{34}	0.29	0.05	-0.16	0.01	-0.06	-0.31	0.15	0.06	-0.16	0.13	1.26
C_{35}	-0.01	0.00	0.02	0.11	0.05	-0.16	0.07	-0.03	0.05	-0.10	-0.22
C_{36}	-0.09	0.12	0.01	0.21	0.13	0.14	0.06	-0.02	0.01	-0.16	-0.05
C_{45}	-0.04	0.06	-0.03	0.11	0.05	0.05	-0.03	-0.02	0.00	-0.09	-0.02
C_{46}	-0.56	0.84	-0.44	2.60	0.35	-1.03	0.59	0.10	-2.30	-0.31	-0.27
C_{56}	0.31	0.41	0.37	0.26	-0.06	-1.08	0.02	0.04	-0.02	2.58	1.91
VPmax	6.86	7.27	7.08	7.93	7.33	6.72	7.11	7.18	7.29	7.18	6.98
VPmin	5.27	5.68	5.75	5.32	5.56	5.48	5.79	5.72	5.51	5.37	5.72
An%	26.2	24.6	20.7	39.4	27.5	20.3	20.5	22.6	27.8	31.4	19.8
dS max	1.02	1.05	0.75	1.77	1.19	0.73	0.77	0.90	1.22	1.28	0.63

1197

1198 Table 5. Different models of elastic properties of Lugo1 slate (C_{ij} in GPa); Wave velocity
 1199 maxima and minima (P and dS velocities are in km/s); P-wave anisotropy coefficient An(%); and
 1200 density (g/cm^3). X is lineation, Z is normal to cleavage. Comparison with Tambo gneiss (Vasin
 1201 et al. 2017), Outokumpu gneiss (Wenk et al. 2012) and Kimmeridge shale (Vasin et al. 2013).

	Lugo1 aggregate C_{ij} $\rho=2.7144 \text{ g/cm}^3$					No Qz ODF	Qz sphere	Tambo 2.660	Outo. 2.750	Kimm 2.648.
	Voigt	Reuss	GMS	GMS	GMS					
Phyllosilicate aspect ratio			0.01	0.1	1	0.1	0.1			
C_{11}	149.1	125.4	140.5	139.8	137.7	139.6	140.6	102.1	105.5	59.0
C_{22}	145.7	119.8	134.5	134.3	133.2	134.1	134.4	90.2	95.4	59.0
C_{33}	88.0	75.7	78.3	78.6	81	78.7	80.2	103.9	78.1	38.1
C_{44}	34.8	26.2	28.8	29.3	30.2	29.3	29.0	33.9	31.8	12.5
C_{55}	34.5	25.7	28.2	28.7	29.7	28.8	28.1	38.3	31.3	12.5
C_{66}	58.5	50.7	54.8	55.0	55.0	54.8	55.0	33.8	39.2	18.8
C_{12}	30.0	20.7	27.4	26.7	25.1	26.7	27.0	25.3	21.5	21.5
C_{13}	18.9	17.2	19.1	18.7	18.0	18.7	17.6	26.8	19.4	20.4
C_{14}	1.0	0.3	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.9	0.0	-0.9	0
C_{15}	-0.6	-0.6	-0.7	-0.7	-0.6	-0.7	-0.9	0.7	1.1	0
C_{16}	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.8	0.9	0
C_{23}	20.0	18.9	20.8	20.2	19.3	20.2	19.7	25.2	21.7	20.4
C_{24}	5.9	5.3	6	5.9	5.7	6.0	6.0	0.4	-0.6	0
C_{25}	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.6	0
C_{26}	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.7	0
C_{34}	0.4	-0.4	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.1	1.1	-1.4	0
C_{35}	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.5	0.3	0
C_{36}	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0
C_{45}	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.3	0.5	0
C_{46}	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	0.2	-0.3	0
C_{56}	2.3	2.5	2.6	2.6	2.4	2.6	2.8	0.3	-3.3	0
VP max	7.41	6.79	7.20	7.18	7.12	7.17	7.20	6.36	6.23	4.60
VP min	5.56	5.24	5.37	5.37	5.44	5.37	5.41	5.90	5.30	3.69
An%	28.5	25.8	29.1	28.8	26.8	28.7	28.4	7.5	16.1	22.0
dS max	1.11	1.28	1.30	1.28	1.22	1.26	1.31	0.25	0.53	0.48

1202

1203

1204 **Supplementary Material**1205 **Supplementary Tables**

1206 Table S1. Geographic Sample coordinates (alphabetical order).

	location	longitude	latitude
Bv5b	Robledo de Domiz	-6.906425°	42.395016°
Heb1	Lardeira	-6.810014°	42.358480°
Fo	Os Follos	-6.752802°	42.309355°
Piv1	Casaio	-6.832466°	42.340085°
Lugo1	Lourixe	-7.341393°	43.171040°
Sa1	Salvatierra De Tormes	-5.597045°	40.587788°

1207

1208

1209 Table S2. Muscovite lattice parameters from MAUD refinement. Standard deviation of last digit
1210 in parentheses.

	a	b	c	γ
Bv5b	20.0819(2)	5.1977(1)	9.0208(2)	95.743(2)
Heb1	20.0927(2)	5.1937(2)	9.0186(3)	95.769(2)
Fo2	20.0897(2)	5.1923(3)	9.0118(3)	95.775(2)
Fo3	20.0948(2)	5.195(2)	9.0164(2)	95.733(2)
Fo4	20.0896(2)	5.1966(1)	9.0155(2)	95.730(2)
Fo7	20.0918(3)	5.1970(2)	9.0177(3)	95.757(2)
Fo8a	20.0927(3)	5.1994(2)	9.0201(3)	95.753(2)
Fo8b	20.0914(3)	5.1979(2)	9.0213(3)	95.760(2)
Fo9	20.0963(2)	5.1961(2)	9.0167(3)	95.770(2)
Piv1	20.0510(3)	5.1858(2)	9.0063(3)	95.734(2)
Lugo1	20.0598(2)	5.2046(2)	9.0316(3)	95.747(2)
Sa1	20.0814(2)	5.1945(9)	9.0173(2)	95.773(1)

1211

1212 Table S3. Muscovite chemistry estimated from SEM-EDS analyses, in percent atomic fraction.

1213 These values are semi-quantitative.

	O	Mg	Al	Si	K	Fe
Bv5b	44.7	1.0	17.7	25.5	8.7	2.4
Heb1	44.9	0.9	15.6	27.6	8.6	2.3
Fo2	47.6	0.0	19.0	24.9	8.5	0.0
Fo3	45.4	0.6	19.0	25.3	9.0	0.7
Fo4	46.1	0.6	18.4	25.4	8.8	0.7
Fo7	45.7	1.2	17.4	25.3	8.6	1.7
Fo8a	45.1	0.7	18.6	25.4	9.0	1.1
Fo8b	45.0	0.9	18.3	25.6	8.6	1.6
Fo9	46.5	0.6	13.7	31.9	6.2	1.1
Piv1	46.0	0.5	17.9	27.5	7.7	0.5
Lugo1	45.3	1.0	17.2	25.6	9.2	1.7
Sa1	46.3	0.6	18.4	24.8	8.9	1.0

1214

1215 Table S4. Chlorite lattice parameters from MAUD refinement. Standard deviation of last digit in
 1216 parentheses.

1217

	a	b	c	α	β	γ
Bv5b	5.3923(2)	9.3150(3)	14.2529(2)	90.000(1)	97.667(3)	90.000(3)
Heb1	5.3064(3)	9.4482(6)	14.1908(2)	91.227(3)	95.432(4)	91.422(5)
Fo2	5.4310(4)	9.3229(6)	14.2111(2)	90.922(4)	96.514(5)	90.744(6)
Fo3	5.3897(3)	9.2841(4)	14.2121(2)	91.024(4)	96.245(4)	89.533(4)
Fo4	5.3677(3)	9.2978(4)	14.2337(2)	91.202(2)	97.077(3)	90.047(4)
Fo7	5.1960(5)	9.3752(9)	14.2963(4)	89.027(3)	98.611(6)	87.231(7)
Fo8a	5.4246(3)	9.3034(7)	14.1938(2)	90.997(3)	95.730(5)	90.277(6)
Fo8b	5.4256(4)	9.3360(6)	14.2009(2)	91.046(3)	95.919(4)	90.351(6)
Fo9	5.4221(3)	9.3182(5)	14.2162(2)	91.188(3)	96.403(2)	90.620(6)
Piv1	5.3743(4)	9.3042(5)	14.2460(2)	92.333(2)	97.412(3)	88.770(4)
Lugo1	5.3787(6)	9.307(1)	14.2497(3)	89.261(3)	97.393(5)	89.65(1)
Sa1	5.3617(3)	9.3092(6)	14.2453(2)	90.531(3)	97.192(5)	89.914(5)

1218

1219 Table S5. Chlorite chemistry estimated from SEM-EDS analyses, in percent atomic fraction.
1220 These values are semi-quantitative.

	O	Mg	Al	Si	Fe
Bv5b	42.9	7.3	14.7	15.5	19.6
Heb1	43.5	7.6	14.6	15.2	19.1
Fo2	44.2	6.9	14.4	14.5	20.0
Fo3	43.4	7.5	14.1	15.4	19.5
Fo4	43.6	7.3	14.5	15.4	19.2
Fo7	43.2	7.4	15.1	15.5	18.8
Fo8a	43.5	7.0	14.4	14.7	20.3
Fo8b	43.8	6.9	14.6	14.7	19.9
Fo9	43.0	7.7	14.6	15.2	19.5
Piv1	42.4	6.4	15.4	14.8	20.9
Lugo1	40.9	7.8	14.6	17.9	18.8
Sa1	44.8	8.5	14.2	14.8	17.8

1221

1222

1223 **Supplementary Figures**1224
1225

1226 Suppl. Fig. 1. Geological map of the Schist-Greywacke Complex (SGC) in the Salvatierra area.
 1227 The location of sample Sa-1 is indicated. NW-SE upright C3 Variscan folds (axial traces)
 1228 dominate the structure in this sector c: conglomerate levels, white dashed lines (after Díez
 1229 Balda et al. 1995).

1230

1231 Suppl. Fig. 2. Geological map (a) and cross section (b) of the sample Lugo-1 in the Mondoñedo
 1232 Nappe Domain. Recumbent C1 folds appear refolded by open upright late Variscan folds (C3).
 1233 Thin-dashed lines in (b) represent S1 foliation pattern (Modified after González Lodeiro et al.
 1234 1979).

1235

1236 Suppl. Fig. 3: Overview of the Truchas syncline roofing slate quarries in the area of study. Note
1237 only the best quality slate is exploited. C: Santa María del Casaio; Fo: Os Follós quarry; R:
1238 Riodaldas; SPT: San Pedro de Trones; PDF: Puente de Domingo Flórez. Source: Google Earth
1239 Pro 7.3.3.7786. (7/12/2019). Santa María del Casaio region; NW Spain. 42°19'39'',N
1240 6°48'15''W, Eye alt 17.26km. Google 2021. <<http://www.google.com/earth/index.html>>
1241 (Accessed August 8, 2021).

1242

1243

1244
1245
1246
1247

Fig. 1 (final)

1248 Fig. 1. (a) Geological map of the Variscan orogen in the Iberian Peninsula. Samples were collected
1249 in three different domains: Sa1 in Schist-Greywacke Complex (SGC), Lugo1 in Mondoñedo
1250 Nappe of WALZ domain and Bv, Heb, Fo and Piv in Ollo de Sapo domain. The location of
1251 the studied areas (red squares) is indicated. The zones of the Variscan Iberian Massif and major
1252 faults and strike-slip shear zones are highlighted (after Martínez Catalán et al., 2014). (b)
1253 Geological map of the Truchas syncline and surrounding areas. (c) Geological section (I-II).
1254 Dashed lines represent axial planes of recumbent folds (C1). C2 Thrusts overprinted C1 folds
1255 and both appear refolded by later C3 upright folds. Red squares: locations of the samples. c)
1256 Stratigraphic legend and ages (after Gutiérrez Marcos et al., 2019).

1257

1258
1259
1260
1261
1262
1263

Fig. 2. Hand specimens of slates. (a) Phyllite Sa1 with crenulation lineation, (b) black slate Os Follos Fo3 with no quartz, (c) slate Fo8 with diagonal bedding (S0) and slaty cleavage (S1) (vertical). Coin with 2cm diameter in (a) is for scale for all.

1264
1265
1266
1267
1268
1269
1270

Fig. 3 Roofing slates: (a) Lugo1, green. (b) Piv1, Luarca Fm. black slate. Slates from Luarca Fm. are very homogeneous. (c) Os Follos Fo9 black-slate (1st quality tiles). In all cases, tile width is 21 cm, thickness varies from 9 mm (Lugo1), 5mm (Piv1) to 2.5 mm (Fo9). Scale is 30 cm.

1271
1272
1273
1274
1275
1276
1277
1278
1279

Fig. 4. Detail of the Os Follós quarry, from where most of our samples were collected (Fo-samples). Slate extraction is focused on the lower part of the quarry (black slates level) just below the Os Follós quartzite (Barros Lorenzo 1989) with minor folds (highlighted in yellow) and S0/S1 relationship (dashed red line).

1280
1281
1282
1283
1284
1285
1286

Fig. 5 (a-l). SEM-BE images of slate samples cut perpendicular to cleavage (XY) and lineation (X). Phases identified using SEM-EDS and labelled as chlorite (C), muscovite (M), quartz (Q), albite (Ab), apatite (Ap) and monazite (Mo). All scale bars are 10 μm unless otherwise labeled. Images were taken in high vacuum mode at a working distance of 15 mm and accelerating voltage of 20 kV.

1287
 1288 Fig. 6 (a-f). SEM-BE images of details in some samples as discussed in the text. Phases
 1289 identified using SEM-EDS are chlorite (C), muscovite (M), quartz (Q), albite (Ab), apatite
 1290 (Ap), biotite (Bi), ilmenite (Il) and monazite (Mo). (g-i) Some details about crenulation
 1291 cleavage in phyllite Sa1. (g) Different domains outlined on the SEM image. (h) Schematic
 1292 outlining microlithon and cleavage domain. Cleavage domain, predominantly defined by
 1293 muscovite, correspond to C3 compressional foliation (S3, red dashed lines). Within
 1294 microlithons transposed relics of the S1 foliation are preserved (blue solid lines). (i) 3D
 1295 image of crenulation and lineation.

1296
1297
1298
1299
1300
1301
1302

Fig. 7. Schematic of X-ray diffraction experiment with X-ray beam, sample mounted on a goniometer head and rotated (ϕ) and detector with diffraction image. Upper left is the pole-figure coverage with 11 images taken at different angles ϕ . Note that there is excellent coverage in the center (X) for the main orientation maximum (001 of phyllosilicates).

1303
1304
1305
1306
1307

Fig. 8. Selected diffraction images for (a) Fo3 (without quartz) and (b) Fo4 (with quartz). Intensity variations along Debye rings are indicative of preferred orientation. In (b) for quartz 100 and 101 there are no intensity variations and thus no CPO. Cleavage plane is vertical.

1308
 1309
 1310
 1311
 1312
 1313
 1314

Fig. 9. “Unrolled” diffraction image of Fo3 (Fig. 13a) in MAUD, plotting azimuthal intensities as function of $2-\Theta$. This corresponds to a stack of 72 integrated diffraction patterns. Some diffraction peaks are indexed. Bottom are experimental data and above it the Rietveld fit.

1315
1316
1317
1318
1319

Fig. 10. Pole-figures of muscovite. Equal area projection on cleavage plane. Contours in multiples of random distribution, logarithmic scale. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are indicated.

1320
1321
1322
1323
1324

Fig. 11. Pole-figures of chlorite. Equal area projection on cleavage plane. Contours in multiples of random distribution, logarithmic scale. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are indicated.

1325
1326
1327

Fig. 12. Pole-figures of quartz. Equal area projection on cleavage plane. Contours in multiples of random distribution, linear scale. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are indicated.

(a) Fo 3 Apatite (001) (b) Sa1 Biotite (001)

1328

1329

Fig. 13. (001) Pole-figures of apatite in Fo3 and biotite in Sa1. Equal area projection on cleavage plane. Contours in multiples of random distribution, linear scale.

1330

1331

1332

1333

1334

1335

1336

1337

Fig. 14. SEM-BE image of microstructure in Fo9 with chlorite (C), muscovite (M) and quartz (Q). Ellipses approximate grain shapes and are used in GeoMixSelf to calculate aggregate elastic properties.

1338

1339

1340

1341

1342

1343

Fig. 15. P-wave velocity distributions of muscovite, chlorite (projected on cleavage plane (001)) and quartz (with c-axis in center) single crystals. Linear scale. Equal area projection. Minimum and maximum velocity values and anisotropy coefficient An are given.

1344

1345

1346 Fig. 16. P and dS velocities, equal area projection on the cleavage plane, linear scale. The first 11

1347 samples are Spanish slates. The last one is Kimmeridge shale from the North Sea for

1348 comparison and with different intensity scale. Anisotropy coefficient An values (%) are

1349 given. Coordinates X (lineation) and Y are indicated.

1350

1351
 1352
 1353
 1354
 1355
 1356
 1357
 1358

Fig. 17. Comparison of muscovite and chlorite texture, represented by maximum values of 001 plane (m.r.d) and tectosilicates (quartz+ Albite) vol%, calculated from data in Table 2. Horizontal grey arrow (1) represents the typical compositional range for Spanish roofing slates, and vertical grey line represents typical tectosilicate content in green phyllites equivalent to Lugo1 (Cardenes et al. 2014).

1359 **Supplementary Figures**

1360

1361

1362

1363 Suppl. Fig. 1 Geological map of the Schist-Greywacke Complex (SGC) in the Salvatierra area.

1364 The location of sample Sa-1 is indicated. NW-SE upright C3 Variscan folds (axial traces)

1365 dominate the structure in this sector (after Díez Balda et al. 1995). c: conglomerate levels,

1366 white dashed lines.

1367

1368

1369
 1370 Suppl. Fig. 2. Geological map (a) and cross section (b) of the sample Lugo-1 in the Mondoñedo
 1371 Nappe Domain. Recumbent C1 folds appear refolded by open upright late Variscan folds (C3).
 1372 (Modified after González Lodeiro et al. 1979). Thin-dashed lines in (b) represent S1 foliation
 1373 pattern.

1374

1375

1376

1377 Suppl. Fig. 3: Overview of the Truchas syncline roofing slate quarries in the area of study. Note
 1378 only the best quality slate is exploited. C: Santa María del Casaio; Fo: Os Follos quarry; R:
 1379 Riodalas; SPT: San Pedro de Trones; PDF: Puente de Domingo Flórez. Source: Google Earth
 1380 Pro 7.3.3.7786. (7/12/2019). Santa María del Casaio region; NW Spain. 42°19'39",N
 1381 6°48'15"W, Eye alt 17.26km. Google 2021. <<http://www.google.com/earth/index.html>>
 1382 (Accessed August 8, 2021).

1383

1384

1385

1386